

Master's Thesis

Double Master in Industrial Engineering and Automatics and Robotics

Positive and Negative sequence analysis of a Voltage Source Converter

REPORT

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Resum

Els components electrònics estan esdevenint essencials per a la xarxa actual i futura, donant serveis útils, a part de la integració de vehicles elèctrics (EV), energies renovables o bateries. Els convertidors de fonts de voltatge (VSC) són una bona opció per mantenir l'estabilitat de la xarxa quan hi ha una falta, el que es coneix com a *Fault-Ride Through* (FRT). En molts casos la falta és desbalancejada, el que afecta directament el control de l'aparell d'electrònica de potència, havent d'afegir un control de seqüència positiva i negativa. Malgrat l'ús de les components simètriques en la literatura, l'explicació del seu significat no és clara. Aquesta tesi vol explicar què són aquestes components i com es poden calcular. A més, l'anàlisi de les components simètriques s'utilitza per intentar obtenir el model de petit senyal de control positiu i negatiu d'un VSC directament des de les seqüències. L'objectiu és utilitzar el model de petit senyal per analitzar l'estabilitat i el disseny dels controls tenint en compte l'efecte de l'asimetria. Aquesta tesi també explica les limitacions de la metodologia presentada degut a l'acoblament entre les components positives i negatives a 0 Hz i 100 Hz. Finalment, el model aconseguit és analitzat per veure les diferències en la dinàmica respecte a un model amb control en seqüència positiva.

Resumen

Los componentes electrónicos se están convirtiendo en esenciales para la red actual y futura, dando servicios útiles, aparte de la integración de vehículos eléctricos (EV), energías renovables o baterías. Los convertidores de fuentes de voltaje (VSC) son una buena opción para mantener la estabilidad de la red cuando existe una falta, lo que se conoce como *Fault-Ride Through* (FRT). En casos donde la falta es desequilibrada, esta afecta directamente al control del aparato de electrónica de potencia, teniendo que añadir un control de secuencia positivo y negativo. Pese al gran uso de las componentes simétricas, en la literatura la explicación de su significado no es fácil de encontrar o entender. Esta tesis quiere explicar qué son estos componentes y cómo pueden calcularse. Además, el análisis de las componentes simétricas es utilizado para intentar obtener modelo de pequeña señal de control positivo y negativo de un VSC, directamente desde las secuencias simétricas. El objetivo es utilizar el modelo de pequeña señal para analizar la estabilidad y el diseño de los controles teniendo en cuenta el efecto de la asimetría. Esta tesis también explica las limitaciones de la metodología presentada debido al acoplamiento entre las componentes positivas y negativas a 0 Hz y 100 Hz. Por último, el modelo obtenido es analizado para ver las diferencias en la dinámica comparado con un modelo con control en secuencia positiva.

Abstract

Power electronic components are becoming essential for the present and future grids, giving useful services apart from integrating electrical vehicles (EV), renewable energies or batteries. Voltage Source Converters (VSCs) are a good option to ensure the stability of the grid when there is a fault, which is known as Fault-Ride Through (FRT). In most cases the fault is unbalanced, which affects directly the control of the power electronic device, having to add a positive and negative sequence control. Despite the wide use of the symmetrical components in the literature, their explanation is not clear in the literature. This thesis aims to explain what are these components and how they can be calculated. Furthermore, the analysis of the symmetrical sequences is used to try to obtain a small-signal model of a VSC with positive and negative control directly from the sequences. The objective is to use the linear model to analyse the stability and design the controls taking into account the effect of the asymmetry. This thesis also explains the limitations of the presented methodology due to the coupling between positive and negative sequence components at 0 Hz and 100 Hz. Finally, the obtained model is analysed to identify the differences in the dynamics with respect to a model with positive sequence control.

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1 Preface

1.1 Origin of the thesis and motivation

The author has been doing research in the electrical and control field for the last two years, learning essential concepts like Park and Clarke transformations or some of the control architectures that are used in converters. During the last year, he has been studying the control of a Multiport Converter (MPC) for unbalanced faults and discovered the positive and negative sequences control and its uses. Despite the application of these controls is clear, it is not straightforward to analyse which is the physical meaning of these symmetrical components and why they have to be applied. As well, in the literature, it is difficult to find an intelligible explanation. This master thesis tries to cover these ideas.

Apart from that, when controllers for an MPC are designed, it is useful to obtain a linear model of the converter, so it can be done a design directly with pole placement or a small-signal analysis. Obtaining the linear model with positive and negative sequences is not an easy task, as normally the linearized models are done in qd components. This master thesis also covers the possibility of creating a linear model of a VSC directly using positive and negative sequences.

1.2 Previous requirements

To do this thesis some requirements are needed. First, Matlab-Simulink knowledge is essential, as it has been used during the thesis to do different simulations and to obtain validations and results. Also, knowledge about some basics of Voltage Source Converters (VSC) has to be known. For example, it is crucial to know the purpose of a Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) or the meaning and uses of qd -components, as they are basic parts of this thesis. However, in the following Sections, the control structure of a VSC is described, to ensure a good understanding of this report by the reader.

2 Introduction

2.1 Positive and negative sequences uses

Positive and negative sequences are used in different fields of electrical engineering [1]. One of their main utilities is to simplify fault analysis, which is essential for protection engineers and technicians[2]. In case of power electronics, and more specifically converters, their main use is when there are unbalanced grids because as it is explained in Section 3, Symmetrical Components transformation converts a balanced or unbalanced system to 3 balanced systems (+, -, 0), so in this way, the control strategies that are normally implemented on a VSC, does not have to be changed [3]. The property that makes these sequences so interesting is that the superposition principle can be applied, as it is always accomplished:

$$i^+ + i^- + i^0 = i, \quad (1)$$

where $i = a, b, c$ phases [4]. So information is no lost about each phase, and apart from that a grid in a, b, c could be represented by three grids in $+, -, 0$ [5], and if their voltages and currents are added will give the same result as the original grid. Thanks to this property, converters could use positive and negative sequences to control the systems when there appear unbalances, as shown in Section 4.

In the literature, some methodologies have been presented to obtain linear models of VSC converters with positive and negative sequence control [6, 7], especially focused on the idea of obtaining a model to calculate the admittance of the converter. The main problem of these publications is the complexity of their methodology, as the linear model is obtained in the complex frame. Apart from that, the Mirror Frequency Decoupled (MFD) property has to be accomplished to obtain the models, which is a significant limitation, as all the controls have to be symmetric. Due to this symmetry requirement, some elements of the control as PLL or outer loops could be incompatible with the MFD property.

The scope of this thesis is to explain in detail these components and their calculation. Once they are explained, it is wanted to study the possibilities of obtaining the linear model directly from qd^{+-} sequences (explained in Section 3) without the requirement to obtain the model with a complex nomenclature.

2.2 Objectives

As is explained in Section 1, the main motivation of this thesis is to better understand what are positive and negative sequences. In the control of a VSC, instead of using directly the positive and negative sequence, qd^{+-} sequences are normally used, which are presented in more detail in Section 3. The objectives of the project are:

- Make a clear explanation of qd^{+-} sequences.
- Analyse the possibility of doing a linear model of a VSC with positive and negative sequence control.
- Analyse if it is required to take into account the negative sequence control for small-signal models.

2.3 Report structure

This thesis is structured as:

- Section 3 explains the positive and negative sequences and how are calculated, focusing especially on the calculation of qd^{+-} sequences components.
- Section 4 shows and validates the control architecture of a VSC with positive and negative sequences.
- Section 5 demonstrates how are linearized the different parts of the VSC converter with positive and negative sequences control.
- Section 6 validate the linear models with the non-linear model that takes into account the coupling and the non-linear model with everything uncoupled. Apart from that, the dynamics of the filter are validated and a linear model with positive sequence is shown.
- Section 7 analyses the differences between the linear model and the non-linear coupled system by doing tests in different scenarios.
- Section 8 analyses the linear model and compares the dynamics with the linear model with only positive sequence.
- Section 9 shows the schedule of this project.
- Section 10 makes a hypothetical budget for the thesis.
- Section 11 explains the environmental impact of the project.
- Section 12 analyses the social and gender impact that this thesis has.
- At the end of this report the obtained conclusions and the future works are explained.

3 Positive and negative sequence calculation

As it is explained in Section 2.2, an essential part of this thesis is to understand which are the qd^{+-} components, also known as positive-negative sequence components, that are widely used in power electronics control. In the literature, two different strategies are explained to calculate qd^{+-} sequences, the first one using the Fortescue calculation [5] and the other strategy using Park transformation [8].

In the following Sections, all the calculations, with their transformations, are explained in detail.

3.1 Fortescue calculation

Using Fortescue calculation, to obtain the qd^{+-} components from an abc frame element, the transformations shown in Figure 1 have to be done [5].

Figure 1: Transformation used to obtain qd^{+-} components.

S is the Fortescue transformation, F is the forward-backwards transformation and C is the complex-real transformation, which are shown in more detail in the following subsections. It is important to mention, that this terminology is the one used in this thesis, however in the literature, there is a lot of variety and sometimes what is named in some articles as $+$, $-$, 0 here is $di, i, 0$ [9] or the combination of f^+, bk^+ is defined as p and the combination of f^-, bk^- is defined as n . [6, 7, 10].

3.1.1 Fortescue transformation

From its definition, time-domain abc voltages could be written as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_a \\ u_b \\ u_c \end{bmatrix} = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \underline{U}_a e^{j\omega t} + \underline{U}_a^* e^{-j\omega t} \\ \underline{U}_b e^{j\omega t} + \underline{U}_b^* e^{-j\omega t} \\ \underline{U}_c e^{j\omega t} + \underline{U}_c^* e^{-j\omega t} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where phasors can be defined as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \underline{U}_a \\ \underline{U}_b \\ \underline{U}_c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} U_a e^{j\alpha_a} \\ U_b e^{j\alpha_b} \\ U_c e^{j\alpha_c} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} U_a \cdot \cos(\alpha_a) + jU_a \cdot \sin(\alpha_a) \\ U_b \cdot \cos(\alpha_b) + jU_b \cdot \sin(\alpha_b) \\ U_c \cdot \cos(\alpha_c) + jU_c \cdot \sin(\alpha_c) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where U_a , U_b and U_c are the magnitudes of the phasors, defined as 400 V in this thesis.

The Fortescue transformation is defined as follows:

$$S = \frac{1}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & a & a^2 \\ 1 & a^2 & a \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}; a = e^{j\frac{2\pi}{3}}. \quad (4)$$

So, the result of applying the Fortescue transformation to the phasors in abc gives the results in the $di, i, 0$ frame which are expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u^{di} \\ u^i \\ u^0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{U}_1 e^{jwt} + \underline{U}_2^* e^{-jwt} \\ \underline{U}_2 e^{jwt} + \underline{U}_1^* e^{-jwt} \\ \underline{U}_0 e^{jwt} + \underline{U}_0^* e^{-jwt} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

where:

$$\underline{U}_1 = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} (\underline{U}_a + a \cdot \underline{U}_b + a^2 \cdot \underline{U}_c) \quad (6)$$

$$\underline{U}_2 = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} (\underline{U}_a + a^2 \cdot \underline{U}_b + a \cdot \underline{U}_c) \quad (7)$$

$$\underline{U}_0 = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} (\underline{U}_a + \underline{U}_b + \underline{U}_c) \quad (8)$$

Therefore:

$$\underline{U}_1 = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} (U_a + U_b + U_c) \quad (9)$$

$$\underline{U}_2 = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} (U_a + U_b \cdot \cos(\frac{2\pi}{3}) + jU_b \cdot \sin(\frac{2\pi}{3}) + U_c \cdot \cos(\frac{-2\pi}{3}) + jU_c \cdot \sin(\frac{-2\pi}{3})) \quad (10)$$

$$\underline{U}_0 = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} (U_a + U_b \cdot \cos(\frac{-2\pi}{3}) + jU_b \cdot \sin(\frac{-2\pi}{3}) + U_c \cdot \cos(\frac{2\pi}{3}) + jU_c \cdot \sin(\frac{2\pi}{3})) \quad (11)$$

If all the voltage phases are balanced and with a magnitude of 400 V,

$$\underline{U}_1 = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} (400 + 400 \cdot (\cos(0) + j\sin(0)) + 400 \cdot (\cos(0) + j\sin(0))) = 282.84, \quad (12)$$

$$\underline{U}_2 = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} (400 + 400 \cdot (\cos(\frac{2\pi}{3}) + j\sin(\frac{2\pi}{3})) + 400 \cdot (\cos(\frac{-2\pi}{3}) + j\sin(\frac{-2\pi}{3}))) = 0, \quad (13)$$

$$\underline{U}_0 = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} (400 + 400 \cdot (\cos(\frac{-2\pi}{3}) + j\sin(\frac{-2\pi}{3})) + 400 \cdot (\cos(\frac{2\pi}{3}) + j\sin(\frac{2\pi}{3}))) = 0, \quad (14)$$

\underline{U}_0 represents the homopolar component. \underline{U}_1 can be understood as the definition of phase a in the positive sequence, which has the same angle as the original representation and is the mean of all the abc components, so if everything is balanced, the value will be the same as in the abc frame. \underline{U}_2 represents phase a in negative sequence, and it is the addition of all the abc components. So, if everything is balanced, the result will be 0, as the addition of all components rotated $\frac{2\pi}{3}$ between them results in 0. However, if the system is unbalanced in phase a for example, \underline{U}_2 represents the increase of this phase.

Sometimes, $di, i, 0$ sequence results are expressed in the literature as $+, -0$, as they represent the results of a phase in each sequence [11]. The main utility of using this Fortescue transformation is that the phasors obtained now could be defined in 3 frames that are always balanced, so, if for example there is a case in which phase a is bigger than phases b and c , with this transformation there will be obtained 3 components that will be always balanced, instead of having the abc frame in which we have one phase voltage bigger than the others. In Figure 2, an example of the $di, i, 0$ components is shown where positive is di and negative is i .

Figure 2: Direct, inverse and 0 sequence definition [12].

To calculate each of the voltages, as u_a^+ is equal to di , u_a^- is i and u_a^0 is 0:

$$\begin{aligned}
\begin{bmatrix} u_a^+ \\ u_a^- \\ u_a^0 \end{bmatrix} &= \frac{1}{3} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & a & a^2 \\ 1 & a^2 & a \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \underline{U}_a \\ \underline{U}_b \\ \underline{U}_c \end{bmatrix}, \\
\begin{bmatrix} u_b^+ \\ u_b^- \\ u_b^0 \end{bmatrix} &= \frac{1}{3} \begin{bmatrix} a^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_a^+ \\ u_a^- \\ u_a^0 \end{bmatrix}, \\
\begin{bmatrix} u_c^+ \\ u_c^- \\ u_c^0 \end{bmatrix} &= \frac{1}{3} \begin{bmatrix} a & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_a^+ \\ u_a^- \\ u_a^0 \end{bmatrix}.
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

An interesting conclusion that could be obtained from the results shown in (5) is that the obtained phasors have the same structure as that with abc frame, but changing the values that rotate forward and backwards, so instead of having each of the phases, the values that rotate are these symmetrical combinations of all the phases. Also, it is crucial to see that the results obtained with this new frame are in a complex range, as it is known that

$$e^{jx} = \cos(x) + j\sin(x). \tag{16}$$

Therefore, the $di, i, 0$ sequence components in temporal range can be defined as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u^{di} \\ u^i \\ u^0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{U}_1(\cos(\omega t) + j\sin(\omega t)) + \underline{U}_2^*(\cos(-\omega t) + j\sin(-\omega t)) \\ \underline{U}_2(\cos(\omega t) + j\sin(\omega t)) + \underline{U}_1^*(\cos(-\omega t) + j\sin(-\omega t)) \\ \underline{U}_0(\cos(\omega t) + j\sin(\omega t)) + \underline{U}_0^*(\cos(-\omega t) + j\sin(-\omega t)) \end{bmatrix}, \tag{17}$$

where $\underline{U}_0, \underline{U}_1$ and \underline{U}_2 are defined in (6),(7) and (8). As U_b is 480 V between 0.2 s and 0.3 s, the following equations are obtained:

$$\underline{U}_1 = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} (400 + 480 \cdot (\cos(0) + j\sin(0)) + 400 \cdot (\cos(0) + j\sin(0))) = 301.69, \tag{18}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{U}_2 &= \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} (400 + 480 \cdot (\cos(\frac{2\pi}{3}) + j\sin(\frac{2\pi}{3})) + \\
&400 \cdot (\cos(\frac{-2\pi}{3}) + j\sin(\frac{-2\pi}{3}))) = -9.428 + j16.33,
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\underline{U}_0 &= \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} (400 + 480 \cdot (\cos(\frac{-2\pi}{3}) + j\sin(\frac{-2\pi}{3})) + \\
&400 \cdot (\cos(\frac{2\pi}{3}) + j\sin(\frac{2\pi}{3}))) = -9.428 - j16.33,
\end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

As u_0 is a combination of \underline{U}_0 and its conjugate with inverse rotation, is always 0. On the other hand, u^{di} and u^i are a combination of \underline{U}_1 and \underline{U}_2 with their conjugate values and inverse rotations. Therefore if (17) is developed, it can be seen that when there is an unbalancing at phase b voltage, the real part amplitude of direct and inverse components is $301.69 - 9.428 = 292.262$ and the amplitude of the imaginary part of direct and inverse components is $301.69 + 9.428 = 311.118$.

In Figure 3, there are shown the results obtained after the Fortescue transformation is applied to a system that has phase b voltage magnitude unbalanced between 0.2 s and 0.3 s:

Figure 3: Fortescue transformation results.

The real and the imaginary values have a phase shift of 90° , but in the di sequence the real part is the first one and in the i sequence it is the imaginary part. So, it can be demonstrated that both sequences are complex numbers conjugated. From (17) it is proven too that di and i components are conjugated. Also, the zero sequence is always 0 except when there is an unbalancing, although it oscillates around 0.

Once the results are obtained in these symmetrical frames, it has been decided to calculate which are the values of \underline{U}_1 and \underline{U}_2 , as shown in Figure 4:

Figure 4: \underline{U}_1 and \underline{U}_2 calculation.

So it is seen that the rotation of the non-conjugated element of each of the $di - i$ frames is deleted and a mean filter is applied to obtain the results without 2nd harmonic oscillations. The used filter is a FIR filter [13]:

$$\frac{1}{T} \frac{1 - e^{sT}}{s}, \quad (21)$$

where T is the period of the grid, 0.02 s. This designed filter has the following Bode plot:

Figure 5: Bode plot of FIR filter.

From Figure 5, it can be seen that this filter deletes all the signals at $k\frac{2\pi}{T}$ rad/s, where k is all the positive integer numbers. So, with this filter, there are deleted all the harmonics, including the second harmonic. The main benefit of this filter is its velocity, as in this case, it deletes the signal in 0.02 s. In this Section, it is used this filter in all the calculations that a mean filter is required. When the system is balanced the the temporal expression obtained after this calculation is defined in (12) and (13). When there is the unbalancing at phase b the amplitude is defined in (18) and (19)

The results obtained in Simulink are the ones shown in Figure 6:

Figure 6: \underline{U}_1 and \underline{U}_2 components.

As it was expected, the results have real and imaginary components, although \underline{U}_1 imaginary part is always 0, except during the transients, as a result of the filter. In the subsection 3.1.3, a deeper analysis of these results is given.

3.1.2 Forward-backward transformation

As it is shown in Figure 1, once there are obtained the $di, i, 0$ components, the calculation of the positive and negative forward-backwards elements can be done. As it is explained in Equation 22 these transformation applies a rotation depending on the angle of the grid.

$$F = \begin{bmatrix} e^{-j\theta} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & e^{j\theta} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (22)$$

As $\theta = \omega t$, it is seen that this transformation will obtain the following results:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u^{f+} \\ u^{b+} \\ u^{0+} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{U}_1 + \underline{U}_2^* e^{-2j\omega t} \\ \underline{U}_2 e^{2j\omega t} + \underline{U}_1^* \\ \underline{U}_0 e^{j\omega t} + \underline{U}_0^* e^{-j\omega t} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (23)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} u^{f-} \\ u^{b-} \\ u^{0-} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{U}_1 e^{2j\omega t} + \underline{U}_2^* \\ \underline{U}_2 + \underline{U}_1^* e^{-2j\omega t} \\ \underline{U}_0 e^{j\omega t} + \underline{U}_0^* e^{-j\omega t} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (24)$$

Analyzing (23) and (24) it can be seen that \underline{U}_1 and \underline{U}_2 are obtained without rotations: \underline{U}_1 in the positive case and \underline{U}_2 in the negative case. So, it can be seen that these transformations are similar to applying the first part of Figure 4 (without mean filter).

In Figures 7 and 8 the results obtained are shown after the forward-backwards positive and negative transformations.

Figure 7: Forward-backward positive transformation.

Figure 8: Forward-backward negative transformation.

Looking at the results obtained by the simulation there can be validated some of the calculations shown in (23) and (24). For example, it is seen that the f sequence and b sequence are conjugated in both cases, as both have the same real values and inverse imaginary values. Also, it is seen that in both cases the 0 sequence is the same as that obtained after the Fortescue transformation.

3.1.3 Complex-real transformation

Finally, the complex-real transformation is done. In (25) it is shown:

$$C = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 \\ j & -j & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (25)$$

To understand better what is done by this transformation, a generic example is shown in (28) and (29), knowing that f^+, f^-, b^+ and b^- are complex numbers. To simplify the understanding there will be shown only the operations in the positive frame, as the procedure is the same. So, it can be seen that f and b are always conjugate in (23) and (24) and in Figures 7 and 8:

$$u^{f^+} = (a + bj) \quad (26)$$

$$u^{b^+} = (a - bj) \quad (27)$$

Therefore:

$$u^{q^+} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (u^{f^+} + u^{b^+}) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (a + bj + a - bj) = a \quad (28)$$

$$u^{d^+} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (ju^{f^+} - ju^{b^+}) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot (aj - b - aj - b) = -b \quad (29)$$

It is clearly shown that what is obtained with this complex-real transformation are the real and the imaginary parts of f^+ and b^+ . So, applying the complex-real transformation to the results obtained after the forward-backward transformation the results are:

$$u^{q^+} = \text{Re}(\underline{U}_1 + \underline{U}_2^* e^{-2j\omega t}), \quad (30)$$

$$u^{d^+} = -\text{Im}(\underline{U}_1 + \underline{U}_2^* e^{-2j\omega t}), \quad (31)$$

$$u^{q^-} = \text{Re}(\underline{U}_1 e^{2j\omega t} + \underline{U}_2^*), \quad (32)$$

$$u^{d^-} = -\text{Im}(\underline{U}_1 e^{2j\omega t} + \underline{U}_2^*). \quad (33)$$

In the case that is being studied, when everything is balanced the results are:

$$u^{q^+} = \text{Re}(\underline{U}_1 + \underline{U}_2^* e^{-2j\omega t}) = \text{Re}(282.84) = 282.84, \quad (34)$$

$$u^{d^+} = -\text{Im}(\underline{U}_1 + \underline{U}_2^* e^{-2j\omega t}) = -\text{Im}(282.84) = 0, \quad (35)$$

$$u^{q^-} = \text{Re}(\underline{U}_1 e^{2j\omega t} + \underline{U}_2^*) = \text{Re}(282.84 e^{2j\omega t}) = 282.84 \cos(2\omega t), \quad (36)$$

$$u^{d-} = -Im(\underline{U}_1 e^{2j\omega t} + \underline{U}_2^*) = -Im(282.84e^{2j\omega t}) = -282.84\sin(2\omega t). \quad (37)$$

When the unbalancing in voltage phase b appears, the results are:

$$u^{q+} = Re(\underline{U}_1 + \underline{U}_2^* e^{-2j\omega t}) = Re(301.69 + (-9.428 + j16.33)e^{-2j\omega t}) = 301.69 - 9.428\cos(-2\omega t) - 16.33\sin(-2\omega t), \quad (38)$$

$$u^{d+} = -Im(\underline{U}_1 + \underline{U}_2^* e^{-2j\omega t}) = -Im(301.69 + (-9.428 + j16.33)e^{-2j\omega t}) = 9.428\sin(-2\omega t) - 16.33\cos(-2\omega t), \quad (39)$$

$$u^{q-} = Re(\underline{U}_1 e^{2j\omega t} + \underline{U}_2^*) = Re(301.69e^{2j\omega t} + (-9.428 - j16.33)) = 301.69\cos(2\omega t) - 9.428, \quad (40)$$

$$u^{d-} = -Im(\underline{U}_1 e^{2j\omega t} + \underline{U}_2^*) = -Im(301.69e^{2j\omega t} + (-9.428 - j16.33)) = -301.69\sin(2\omega t) + 16.33. \quad (41)$$

Returning to the results obtained after the calculation done in Figure 4, it can be seen that what is obtained after this complex transformation is quite similar. However, in this case, the results obtained are before the mean filter. Also, the only objective of this transformation is to convert the complex number into $q, d, 0$ form. In Figure 9 there are shown the results:

(a) $u^{q^+d^+0^+}$.

(b) $u^{q^-d^-0^-}$.

Figure 9: $qd0$ components.

It is seen that there are oscillations when unbalances appear, so the mean filter is applied to delete these undesired oscillations. The numerical results when the system is balanced are:

$$u^{q^+} = 282.84 ; u^{d^+} = 0, \quad (42)$$

$$u^{q^-} = 0 ; u^{d^-} = 0. \quad (43)$$

Otherwise, when the unbalance appear the voltages are:

$$u^{q^+} = 301.69 ; u^{d^+} = 0, \quad (44)$$

$$u^{q^-} = -9.428 ; u^{d^-} = 16.33. \quad (45)$$

The results obtained from the simulation are shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: qd0 components.

Finally, there are compared in Figures 11 and 12 the qd^{+-} and the real and imaginary values of \underline{U}_1 and \underline{U}_2 obtained in (6) and (7).

Figure 11: Comparison positive components.

Figure 12: Comparison negative components.

It is seen that the signals are exactly the same, so, it can be seen that qd^{+-} values are the real and imaginary parts of \underline{U}_1 and \underline{U}_2 from the symmetrical transformation after applying the mean filter. Also, as the real and imaginary components have always 90 degrees between them, the orthogonality is ensured as it happens with qd components. The forward-backward and complex-real transformations are only used to obtain these real and imaginary components that are what are named qd^{+-} components.

3.1.4 Magnitude calculation

Another interesting application of the study that has been done of the sequences in this thesis is that the magnitudes in the steady state of q^+ , d^+ , q^- and d^- could be calculated.

To calculate the magnitudes there are used the \underline{U}_1 and \underline{U}_2 signals in cosine and sine form, as shown in (9) and (10).

So in (9) it is seen that there is no imaginary component and the real part will always be the mean of the peak voltage of each of the phases.

$$u^{q+} = \frac{1}{3} \cdot (U_a + U_b + U_c), \quad (46)$$

$$u^{d+} = 0. \quad (47)$$

On the other hand from (10) the real and imaginary parts are (q^- and d^-):

$$u^{q-} = \frac{1}{3} \cdot (U_a \cdot \cos(0) + U_b \cdot \cos(\frac{2\pi}{3}) + U_c \cdot \cos(\frac{4\pi}{3})), \quad (48)$$

$$u^{d-} = \frac{1}{3} \cdot (U_b \cdot \sin(\frac{2\pi}{3}) + U_c \cdot \sin(\frac{4\pi}{3})). \quad (49)$$

Knowing these values of the sinus and the cosinus it can be seen that:

$$u^{q+} = \frac{1}{3} \cdot (U_a + U_b + U_c) \quad (50)$$

$$u^{d+} = 0 \quad (51)$$

$$u^{q-} = \frac{1}{3} \cdot (U_a - \frac{U_b}{2} - \frac{U_c}{2}) \quad (52)$$

$$u^{d-} = \frac{1}{3} \cdot (\frac{\sqrt{3}U_b}{2} - \frac{\sqrt{3}U_c}{2}) \quad (53)$$

It is proven that when everything is balanced all the values of the negative part will be 0. Also, an useful obtained information is that the 3 abc phases can define the value of the qd^{+-} components in a steady state, as it is a consistent dependent system of equations with 3 equations and 3 unknowns. These equations are used in the linear model to calculate the inputs.

3.2 Park calculation

The second option found in the literature is to calculate qd^{+-} sequences using Park transformation [8, 14]. Park transformation is defined as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u^q \\ u^d \\ u^0 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & \cos(\theta - \frac{2\pi}{3}) & \cos(\theta + \frac{2\pi}{3}) \\ \sin(\theta) & \sin(\theta - \frac{2\pi}{3}) & \sin(\theta + \frac{2\pi}{3}) \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_a \\ u_b \\ u_c \end{bmatrix}. \quad (54)$$

Figure 13 shows how are the sequences obtained in this particular case.

Figure 13: qd^{+-} sequence extraction. Source [8].

Where MAF is a Moving Average Filter. In this case, it is seen that qd^{+-} sequences could be understood as the Park transformation of an abc signal rotating 50 Hz and the abc signal rotating -50 Hz. Due to the MAFs, the qd^- sequence is 0 when everything is balanced, as the signals obtained by the Park transformation are sinusoidal waves of 100 Hz around 0. When some unbalancing appears, one or both sinusoidal waves (q^- or d^-) have a bias that makes the final signal different to 0. In Figure 14 there are shown the signals obtained when there is an unbalancing of phase b magnitude between 0.2 s and 0.3 s, as it has been done with the Fortescue calculation.

Figure 14: qd components.

It can be seen that the results are as in the case of the Fortescue calculation. It is important to mention that the MAFs filters used in this Section are FIR filters, which is important because, in the following Sections, it is shown that this uncoupling filter has a relevant importance on the system. Park calculation of qd^{+-} is widely used due to its simplicity, so in this thesis, the objective is to linearize the model using this calculation.

3.2.1 Comparison with the Fortescue calculation

Comparing the Park transformation (54) with the calculation of Section 3.1 it is seen that the same operations are done, as there is always applied a rotation of θ or $-\theta$ and in the case of the bc sequences is also applied a rotation of $\frac{2\pi}{3}$ or $-\frac{2\pi}{3}$. In Section 3.1 it is also used the complex-real transformation, but it is a transformation that is only used to catch the results in qd frame, as the results are obtained in the complex plane.

Once both calculations are understood, an idea of what are qd^{+-} sequences and why are used is obtained. qd^{+-} sequences components divide the system (Fortescue transformation) to ensure that the subsystems are always balanced. Thanks to the balance of the subsystems and the MAFs, the qd^{+-} components do not have oscillations. As qd^{+-} signals can be overlapped [4], the control techniques developed for the VSCs only have to be duplicated, as shown in Section 4.

4 VSC with positive-negative control

4.1 Introduction of the studied system

In the following Sections, the main objective is to linearize a VSC taking into account the positive-negative sequence control that is being used. The use of the negative sequence is essential when there are studies with unbalanced grids, as the control architecture that is presented in the following lines can ensure the stability of the system.

Figure 15 shows the general structure of the used control.

Figure 15: Control structure studied.

The VSC is modelled as an average model. As it is seen in Figure 15, the controller is as most of the control architectures shown in the literature [15, 16], but has the inner current loop control twice, one for the positive sequence and another for the negative sequence. In the positive sequence, the reference is obtained from the active and reactive powers, and in the negative case, the reference is defined always as 0 [17]. The voltages obtained by these loops are added, obtaining the voltage that is used in the converter as the control variable. To calculate the qd^{+-} components it has been used the Park transformation and the filter that is explained in detail in Section 4.2.3.

4.2 Control structures description

The control structures that appear in the system are explained in the following lines.

4.2.1 Reference current calculation

The system defined is a cascaded control, in which the reference current calculation is the outer loop. In this section of the controller, from the reference values of the active and the reactive power, the reference values of the currents are obtained.

To obtain the relationship between the powers and the current values in the qd frame, some calculations must be made, as it has been extensively explained in [15].

Firstly, if the Park transformation is applied, the voltage and current phasors in qd are

$$\underline{V}^{qd} = \frac{v_q - jv_d}{\sqrt{2}}; \quad \underline{I}^{qd} = \frac{i_q - ji_d}{\sqrt{2}}. \quad (55)$$

The power of a three-phase system is

$$\underline{S} = P + jQ = 3\underline{V}^{qd} \underline{I}^{qd*} = 3 \left(\frac{v_q - jv_d}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \left(\frac{i_q + ji_d}{\sqrt{2}} \right). \quad (56)$$

If (56) is reordered it is found that the active and reactive powers have the following structure:

$$P = \frac{3}{2}(v_q i_q + v_d i_d); \quad Q = \frac{3}{2}(v_q i_d - v_d i_q). \quad (57)$$

As it is explained in Section 4.2.4, v_d is controlled at 0. So if the reference value of the powers is known, the value of the reference currents is defined as

$$i_q^{+*} = \frac{2P^*}{3v_q}; \quad i_d^{+*} = \frac{2Q^*}{3v_q} \quad (58)$$

$$i_q^{-*} = 0; \quad i_d^{-*} = 0 \quad (59)$$

However, in this thesis, there are qd positive and negative values, so the reference has to be calculated in both sequences. There have been found in the literature different ways to calculate the references [17], but probably the widely used technique is to always define the negative reference currents as 0 [18].

So, it has been decided to define the positive qd reference currents as it has been done in (59), and the negative references as 0. In Figure 16 the definition of this structure has been drawn.

Figure 16: Reference calculation.

4.2.2 Inner current control

Once the reference values of the current are obtained inner current control is implemented. This control structure is widely used in the VSCs, as it is shown in the literature [19].

In the case of this thesis, as it has been explained in Section 4.1, there are two current controls, one for the positive sequence and another one for the negative sequence. They have the same structure but vary between the positive and negative parameters. For a better understanding Figure 17 shows both loops.

Figure 17: Inner current control loops.

As can be seen, the parameters of the PI controllers have to be defined, which depend on how this loop has been defined. This method is based on the decoupling and independent controlling of q and d components. This decoupling can be defined as

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{lq} \\ v_{ld} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\hat{v}_{lq} + v_{zq} - l_l \omega_e i_{ld} \\ -\hat{v}_{ld} + l_l \omega_e i_{lq} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (60)$$

where \hat{v}_{lq} and \hat{v}_{ld} are the outputs of the current controllers and v_{lq} and v_{ld} are the voltages that are applied by the converter. If the equations are rewritten,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \hat{v}_{lq} \\ \hat{v}_{ld} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} r_l & 0 \\ 0 & r_l \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_q \\ i_d \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} l_l & 0 \\ 0 & l_l \end{bmatrix} \frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} i_q \\ i_d \end{bmatrix}. \quad (61)$$

Once voltage relationships are obtained there can be found the transfer functions between the controller voltages and the converter currents as

$$\frac{\hat{v}_{lq}(s)}{i_q(s)} = \frac{1}{l_l s + r_l}; \quad \frac{\hat{v}_{ld}(s)}{i_d(s)} = \frac{1}{l_l s + r_l}. \quad (62)$$

Using the Internal Model Control technique [15], the controller used with this architecture could be defined as

$$G_{ciq}(s) = G_{cid}(s) = \frac{K_p s + K_i}{s}, \quad (63)$$

defining the proportional and integral gains as

$$K_p = \frac{l_l}{\tau}; K_i = \frac{r_l}{\tau}. \quad (64)$$

where τ is the closed loop time constant of the electrical system, 1 ms in this thesis. The gains will be the same for both loops as both have the same structure and parameters.

4.2.3 Notch Filter

To obtain qd^{+-} sequences there are different possible calculations. In the literature, it is common to obtain the results from $\alpha\beta 0$ sequences [22]. In this case,

$$\begin{bmatrix} x^{\alpha\beta+}(s) \\ x^{\alpha\beta-}(s) \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -H(s) \\ H(s) & 1 \\ 1 & H(s) \\ -H(s) & 1 \end{bmatrix} x^{\alpha\beta}(s); H(s) = \frac{s - \omega_e}{s + \omega_e}, \quad (65)$$

where ω_e is $2\pi f_e$, being f_e the frequency of the grid (50 Hz in this thesis). Once the $\alpha\beta 0^{+-}$ sequences are obtained, it is only required to apply the transformation between $\alpha\beta 0$ and $qd 0$.

However, as the linearization is done directly at qd^{+-} sequences, it is necessary to use a relationship coming from qd sequence, as shown in Section 3.2.

A Moving Average Filter can be defined as:

$$\bar{x}(t) = \frac{1}{T_w} \int_{t-T_w}^t x(\tau) d\tau \quad (66)$$

T_w is the window of the MAF and is proven that in the case of unbalancing if $T_w = T/2$, being T the grid period, the second-order harmonics are removed [8]. In this thesis, the frequency of the grid is 50 Hz, so T is 0.02 s and $T_w = 0.01$ s. In the case of the qd sequences, the MAF could be understood as the mean between the actual value in qd and the value T_w seconds before. FIR filters are used in Section 3, however they need a Padé approximation to be linearized, which may be a problem. So, assuming that the responses after the Park transformations have a sinusoidal form, MAF could also be written as:

$$\frac{1}{2}(1 + F(s))u; F(s) = \frac{(s - 2\omega_e)^2}{(s + 2\omega_e)^2}, \quad (67)$$

being u the entrance of the MAF. $F(s)$ takes its value 180° before at frequencies relative to $2\omega_e$ rad/s, as the objective of the filter is to delete the second-order harmonics. Figure 18 shows the Bode plot of the transfer function.

Figure 18: Bode plot of $F(s)$

As it can be seen, this filter ensures that at a frequency of $2\pi 100$, the phase is 180° and the gain is 0. So, as the phase is 180° , $F(s)$ takes the value of the input, 0.1 s before (as the input has a period of 0.2 s).

The relationship between qd^{+-} and qd could be written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x^{q+}(s) \\ x^{d+}(s) \\ x^{q-}(s) \\ x^{d-}(s) \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 + F(s) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 + F(s) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 + F(s) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 + F(s) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x^q(\theta^+)(s) \\ x^d(\theta^+)(s) \\ x^q(\theta^-)(s) \\ x^d(\theta^-)(s) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (68)$$

(68) shows that the relationship used to calculate the qd^{+-} sequences is linear and that it adds dynamics to the system. Figure 19 shows the bode plot that $\frac{1}{2}(1 + F(s))$ has, which is a notch filter behaviour.

Figure 19: Bode plot of $\frac{1}{2}(1 + F(s))$ filter.

4.2.4 Phase Locked Loop

Finally, it is important to define the Phase Locked Loop (PLL) and its importance. In this thesis, it has been decided that the converter will be working in grid-following mode, so, it is necessary to estimate the angle of the electrical network. A PLL structure is used to achieve this objective. The PLL scheme used is the typical SRF architecture used in the literature [20], which is defined in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Phase Locked Loop (PLL).

To study how are the parameters used in the controllers of the PLL, it is defined a second-order system that relates the real grid angle (θ) with the estimated angle ($\hat{\theta}$) by the PLL, assuming that the error between them is small,

$$\frac{\hat{\theta}(s)}{\theta(s)} = \frac{2\xi\omega_n s + \omega_n^2}{s^2 + 2\xi\omega_n s + \omega_n^2}. \quad (69)$$

Based on [15], the PLL controller can be defined as

$$K_f(s) = K_p \left(\frac{1}{\tau_{PLL}} + s \right), \quad (70)$$

being τ_{PLL} the PLL time constant. The parameters K_p and τ_{PLL} can be computed using equations

$$\omega_n = \sqrt{\frac{K_p E_m}{\tau_{PLL}}}; \quad \xi = \frac{\sqrt{\tau_{PLL} K_p E_m}}{2}, \quad (71)$$

where E_m is the admitted peak voltage value, ξ is the damping ratio and ω_n is the electrical angular velocity. Therefore, the constant gain (K_p^{PLL}) and the PLL time constant (τ_{PLL}) are:

$$K_p^{PLL} = \frac{2\omega_n \xi}{E_m}; \quad \tau_{PLL} = \frac{2\xi}{\omega_n}, \quad (72)$$

In this thesis, the damping ratio (ξ) chosen is $\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$ and the PLL time constant (τ_{PLL}) is 0.025 s.

4.3 Validation of the control in normal operation

To show that this control strategy operates correctly, the results are tested in a LV case in two different scenarios:

- Active and reactive reference powers are changing their values during the simulation.
- Negative current reference is changing its value.

The second scenario is used to demonstrate that the VSC control works as expected when there are negative currents different to 0, even Section 4.2.2 explains that the negative current references are defined as 0 in this thesis.

4.3.1 Powers variation

Figures 21, 22 and 23 show the results of the first test.

Figure 21: Powers in normal operation.

Figure 22: Positive currents in normal operation.

Figure 23: Negative currents in normal operation.

As it can be seen in Figures 21, 22 and 23 the reference values of the powers and the positive currents are followed as expected.

4.3.2 Negative currents variation

In this test, negative currents are changed between different positive values. Figures 24, 25 and 26 show the results.

Figure 24: Powers in normal operation.

Figure 25: Positive currents in normal operation.

Figure 26: Negative currents in normal operation.

Figure 24 shows that when negative currents are different to 0, the powers oscillate, as it is expected in VSCs with negative current control. Figure 25 displays the positive currents, which are constant during all the simulation except when there are changes in the negative currents references. Finally, Figure 26 demonstrates that the negative currents follow its references. So, it is concluded that the control structure works in normal operation.

5 Linear model of the VSC converter

To linearize the whole system the equations of the different blocks were calculated and after that, it was created a unique system with the help of Matlab. To do these calculations the equilibrium points have to be found too, so the values in steady state were taken with the help of the *trimming* Matlab function.

The main characteristic of the positive and negative sequences is that they can be uncoupled [4, 20]. Due to this property, two different studies are done in this thesis:

- A non-linear model without decoupling the grid in positive and negative sequence (Figure 27).
- A non-linear model with the grids and the control decoupled (Figure 28).

Figure 27: Coupled variables structure.

In the following subsections are explained the procedures done in each of the control structures to obtain the linear model. To linearize the non-linear terms of each block the Taylor expansion is used at their operation points [21].

Figure 28: Uncoupled variables structure.

5.1 Positive and negative sequence calculation of reference grid voltages

To uncouple the real grid in positive and negative grids (Figure 28), first, it is required to calculate the values of the grid in abc^{+-} . The relationship between abc and abc^{+-} is the Fortescue transformation (4). So, to calculate each of the grid voltages it is used the relationship explained in Section 3.1.

To calculate positive and negative values of phase b and c , there are used the obtained results of phase $di, i, 0$ sequence. *Simulink* has a block (*Symmetrical Components Transformation*) that applies the Fortescue transformation (15), however, it gives the results in the complex domain. To simplify the calculation, as a is applying a rotation of $2\pi/3$ radians, it has been directly applied the rotation to the reference grid values.

5.2 Filter

As the notch filter used adds dynamics to the system, it has to be considered in the linear model. The filter structure is linear, so the state space will be directly obtained from its transfer function:

$$N(s) = \frac{s^2 + (2\omega_e)^2}{s^2 + 4\omega_e s + (\omega_e)^2} = \frac{Y(s)}{E(s)}. \quad (73)$$

Therefore, the space state of the notch filter is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_1^f \\ \dot{x}_2^f \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -4\omega_e & (2\omega_e)^2 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x_1^f \\ x_2^f \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} e, \quad (74)$$

$$y = \begin{bmatrix} -4\omega_e & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x_1^f \\ x_2^f \end{bmatrix} + e, \quad (75)$$

where e is the entrance of the filter and y the output of the filter. x_1^f and x_2^f are the states of each filter.

5.3 Transformations and rotation matrices

In the linear model, it is not required to apply any transformation as it is assumed that the model is in $qd0^{+-}$. However, due to the use of a PLL, which has an error in the estimation of the angle, the rotational matrices are used in the linear model to switch between two reference frames: control and grid frame [21]. The grid values are all the signals that are measured directly from the grid and the control frame has all the signals that are obtained after applying a rotation with the angle obtained by the PLL. The angle that links the PLL and the grid is defined as θ_e and is:

$$\theta_e = \theta_{PLL} - \theta_{grid}, \quad (76)$$

being θ_{PLL} the output of the PLL and θ_{grid} the measured angle of the grid. So, the relationship between the signals in control and grid frames could be defined as:

$$\mathbf{x}_{qd}^{c+-} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_e) & -\sin(\theta_e) \\ \sin(\theta_e) & \cos(\theta_e) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \mathbf{x}_{qd}^{+-}, \quad (77)$$

where \mathbf{x}_{qd}^{c+-} is the current or the voltage in control frame and \mathbf{x}_{qd}^{+-} in grid frame. As can be seen, the matrix that relates the frames is non-linear, so it has to be linearized. However, before that, it is necessary to calculate a relationship related to θ_e :

$$\dot{\theta}_e^+ = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{PLL} \\ \omega_{grid} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (78)$$

As θ_e is the state of the linear system, its output is directly this signal. In the case of the calculation of θ_e for the negative sequence control the structure is the same but multiplied by -1:

$$\dot{\theta}_e^- = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{PLL} \\ \omega_{grid} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (79)$$

In the system used in this thesis the following rotations have to be done:

- Voltage from control frame to voltage in grid frame.
- Current from control frame to current in grid frame.
- Voltage from grid frame to control frame.

So there it has to be linearized the matrix from (77) and its inverse. The results of these linearizations are:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_q^{c+} \\ x_d^{c+} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_{e0}^+) & -\sin(\theta_{e0}^+) & -\sin(\theta_{e0}^+) \cdot x_{q0}^+ - \cos(\theta_{e0}^+) \cdot x_{d0}^+ \\ \sin(\theta_{e0}^+) & \cos(\theta_{e0}^+) & \cos(\theta_{e0}^+) \cdot x_{q0}^+ - \sin(\theta_{e0}^+) \cdot x_{d0}^+ \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x_q^+ \\ x_d^+ \\ \theta_e^+ \end{bmatrix}, \quad (80)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_q^{c-} \\ x_d^{c-} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_{e0}^-) & -\sin(\theta_{e0}^-) & -\sin(\theta_{e0}^-) \cdot x_{q0}^- - \cos(\theta_{e0}^-) \cdot x_{d0}^- \\ \sin(\theta_{e0}^-) & \cos(\theta_{e0}^-) & \cos(\theta_{e0}^-) \cdot x_{q0}^- - \sin(\theta_{e0}^-) \cdot x_{d0}^- \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x_q^- \\ x_d^- \\ \theta_e^- \end{bmatrix}, \quad (81)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_q^+ \\ x_d^+ \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_{e0}^+) & \sin(\theta_{e0}^+) & -\sin(\theta_{e0}^+) \cdot x_{q0}^{c+} + \cos(\theta_{e0}^+) \cdot x_{d0}^{c+} \\ -\sin(\theta_{e0}^+) & \cos(\theta_{e0}^+) & -\cos(\theta_{e0}^+) \cdot x_{q0}^{c+} - \sin(\theta_{e0}^+) \cdot x_{d0}^{c+} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x_q^{c+} \\ x_d^{c+} \\ \theta_e^+ \end{bmatrix}, \quad (82)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_q^- \\ x_d^- \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_{e0}^-) & \sin(\theta_{e0}^-) & -\sin(\theta_{e0}^-) \cdot x_{q0}^{c-} + \cos(\theta_{e0}^-) \cdot x_{d0}^{c-} \\ -\sin(\theta_{e0}^-) & \cos(\theta_{e0}^-) & -\cos(\theta_{e0}^-) \cdot x_{q0}^{c-} - \sin(\theta_{e0}^-) \cdot x_{d0}^{c-} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x_q^{c-} \\ x_d^{c-} \\ \theta_e^- \end{bmatrix}, \quad (83)$$

where x is the voltages and currents.

5.4 Reference current calculation

Section 4.2.1 shows that in this block the inputs are the reference values of active and reactive power and v_q^+ . Applying Taylor expansions there could be obtained the following relationships:

$$i_q^{*+} = \frac{2 \cdot P^*}{3 \cdot U_{q0}^{c+}} - \frac{2 \cdot P_0 \cdot u_q^{c+}}{3 \cdot U_{q0}^{c+2}}, \quad (84)$$

$$i_d^{*+} = \frac{2 \cdot Q^*}{3 \cdot U_{q0}^{c+}} - \frac{2 \cdot Q_0 \cdot u_q^{c+}}{3 \cdot U_{q0}^{c+2}}. \quad (85)$$

Where P_0 , V_{q0}^+ and Q_0 are the steady state values of these signals. Once these equations are obtained the linear state space of both expressions is:

$$i_q^{*+} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2}{3 \cdot U_{q0}^{c+}} & -\frac{2 \cdot P_0}{3 \cdot U_{q0}^{c+2}} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} P^* \\ u_q^{c+} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (86)$$

$$i_d^{*+} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2}{3 \cdot U_{q0}^{c+}} & -\frac{2 \cdot Q_0}{3 \cdot U_{q0}^{c+2}} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} Q^* \\ u_q^{c+} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (87)$$

5.5 Inner current control

In the case of the inner current control blocks, the linear model between the positive and negative parts varies, as the angular velocities have different signs between the positive and negative parts. Due to the PI controllers, the states of the system (x_{i1}^+ and x_{i2}^+) are the derivatives of the error between the references and the measurements. The state space obtained in the positive grid is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_{i1}^+ \\ \dot{x}_{i2}^+ \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} i_q^{*+} \\ i_d^{*+} \\ i_q^{c+} \\ i_d^{c+} \\ u_q^{c+} \\ u_d^{c+} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (88)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} U_q^{c+} \\ U_d^{c+} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -K i_{cl} & 0 \\ 0 & -K i_{cl} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x_{i1}^+ \\ x_{i2}^+ \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -K p_{cl} & 0 & K p_{cl} & -\omega \cdot L_l & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -K p_{cl} & \omega \cdot L_l & K p_{cl} & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} i_q^{*+} \\ i_d^{*+} \\ i_q^{c+} \\ i_d^{c+} \\ u_q^{c+} \\ u_d^{c+} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (89)$$

For the negative part, the model is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_{i1}^- \\ \dot{x}_{i2}^- \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} i_q^{*-} \\ i_d^{*-} \\ i_q^{c-} \\ i_d^{c-} \\ u_q^{c-} \\ u_d^{c-} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (90)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} U_q^{c-} \\ U_d^{c-} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -K i_{cl} & 0 \\ 0 & -K i_{cl} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x_{i1}^- \\ x_{i2}^- \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -K p_{cl} & 0 & K p_{cl} & \omega \cdot L_l & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -K p_{cl} & -\omega \cdot L_l & K p_{cl} & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} i_q^{*-} \\ i_d^{*-} \\ i_q^{c-} \\ i_d^{c-} \\ u_q^{c-} \\ u_d^{c-} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (91)$$

As the reference of the currents is 0, i_q^{*-} and i_d^{*-} will be directly 0. However, if these inputs are not defined, it would not be possible to do tests injecting only negative current.

5.6 PLL

As it happens with the Inner current control, the PI controller is defined creating a complementary state which is defined as x_{PLL} , so the space state block used after the linearization for the

PLL is:

$$\dot{x}_{PLL}^+ = u_d^{c+}, \quad (92)$$

$$\omega_{PLL} = -K i_{PLL} \cdot x_{PLL}^+ - K p_{PLL} \cdot u_d^{c+}. \quad (93)$$

It is important to mention that as in the non-linear model, the angular velocity used is the same for the positive and the negative sequences, but changing only the sign, in the linear model in the negative part it is used the angular velocity obtained from this PLL multiplied by -1.

5.7 Delay

Time-domain simulations sometimes need some unit delays to avoid algebraic loops that will create some Inf or Nan values that will stop the simulation. In the case of the model that is developed in this thesis, there are added unit delays after the Inner current control blocks to avoid the mentioned algebraic loops.

As a delay is a non-linear term, it has to be linearized. In the literature different solutions are proposed, however, the most used solution is the Padé approximation. To define the function there are required the delayed time and the order of the transfer function [23]:

$$e^{-\theta s} = \frac{(1 - \frac{\theta}{2n} s)^n}{(1 + \frac{\theta}{2n} s)^n}. \quad (94)$$

The delay time has been defined as 0.1 ms, as it is a value that agrees with the solver details. On the other hand, if the order is high, the approximation will be more precise. However, for big order values the computation time will increase, so a compromise is needed. It has been decided to use the Padé approximation of order 20, as the computation time is acceptable and the order will add as less dynamics as possible.

5.8 Converter

Finally, the linearization of the grid until the PCC has to be done. In this case, the space state obtained for the positive sequence is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{i} s_q^+ \\ \dot{i} s_d^+ \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-(R_{eq}+R_l)}{L_{eq}+L_l} & -\omega \\ \omega & \frac{-R_{eq}+R_l}{L_{eq}+L_l} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} i s_q^+ \\ i s_d^+ \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-1}{L_{eq}+L_l} & 0 & \frac{1}{L_{eq}+L_l} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{-1}{L_{eq}+L_l} & 0 & \frac{1}{L_{eq}+L_l} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} u_q^{cc+} \\ u_d^{cc+} \\ u_q^{TH+} \\ u_d^{TH+} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (95)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_{s_q^+} \\ i_{s_d^+} \\ u_q^+ \\ u_d^+ \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \\ \frac{-R_{eq}+L_{eq} \cdot (R_l+R_{eq})}{L_l+L_{eq}} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{-R_{eq}+L_{eq} \cdot (R_l+R_{eq})}{L_l+L_{eq}} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} i_{s_q^+} \\ i_{s_d^+} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{L_{eq}}{L_l+L_{eq}} & 0 & \frac{1-L_{eq}}{L_l+L_{eq}} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{L_{eq}}{L_l+L_{eq}} & 0 & \frac{1-L_{eq}}{L_l+L_{eq}} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} u_q^{cc+} \\ u_d^{cc+} \\ u_q^{TH+} \\ u_d^{TH+} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (96)$$

And for the negative sequence is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{i}_{s_q^-} \\ \dot{i}_{s_d^-} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-(R_{eq}+R_l)}{L_{eq}+L_l} & \omega \\ -\omega & \frac{-R_{eq}+R_l}{L_{eq}+L_l} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} i_{s_q^-} \\ i_{s_d^-} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-1}{L_{eq}+L_l} & 0 & \frac{1}{L_{eq}+L_l} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{-1}{L_{eq}+L_l} & 0 & \frac{1}{L_{eq}+L_l} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} u_q^{cc-} \\ u_d^{cc-} \\ u_q^{TH-} \\ u_d^{TH-} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (97)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} i_{s_q^-} \\ i_{s_d^-} \\ u_q^- \\ u_d^- \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \\ \frac{-R_{eq}+L_{eq} \cdot (R_l+R_{eq})}{L_l+L_{eq}} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{-R_{eq}+L_{eq} \cdot (R_l+R_{eq})}{L_l+L_{eq}} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} i_{s_q^-} \\ i_{s_d^-} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{L_{eq}}{L_l+L_{eq}} & 0 & \frac{1-L_{eq}}{L_l+L_{eq}} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{L_{eq}}{L_l+L_{eq}} & 0 & \frac{1-L_{eq}}{L_l+L_{eq}} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} u_q^{cc-} \\ u_d^{cc-} \\ u_q^{TH-} \\ u_d^{TH-} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (98)$$

5.9 Combination of linear model blocks

Once there are obtained the state space of all the blocks that define the studied system, a linear model is created with the help of Matlab and the function *connect*. Appendix A shows the code used to create the linear models. The inputs and outputs are defined in this section. Inputs are:

- Active power reference P^*
- Reactive power reference Q^*
- Active negative current reference i_q^{*-}
- Reactive negative current reference i_d^{*-}
- positive q-component of the grid voltage u_q^{TH+}

- positive d-component of the grid voltage u_d^{TH+}
- negative q-component of the grid voltage u_q^{TH-}
- negative d-component of the grid voltage u_d^{TH-}
- Angular velocity of the grid ω^*

The outputs of the linear model are the signals that are compared with the non-linear models. They are:

- positive q-component of the grid current i_q^{c+}
- positive d-component of the grid current i_d^{c+}
- positive q-component of the PLL voltage u_q^{c+}
- positive d-component of the PLL voltage u_d^{c+}
- negative q-component of the grid current i_q^{c-}
- negative d-component of the grid current i_d^{c-}
- negative q-component of the PLL voltage u_q^{c-}
- negative d-component of the PLL voltage u_d^{c-}
- positive angular velocity of the PLL ω_{PLL}^+

The model has 107 states. Figure 29 shows a resume of how is the linear model created. Once the outputs are obtained, the comparison between the linear and non-linear models could be done.

Figure 29: Summary of linear model.

6 Linear model validation

The validation has been done with the non-linear grids coupled and uncoupled. The parameters used are:

Parameter	Value
Nominal AC grid voltage	400 V
Nominal port converter power	300 kVA
SCR	20
R/X	10
P^*	0.66 p.u.
Q^*	0.33 p.u.
$R_l + jL_l$	0.01+j0.2 p.u.

6.1 Model with only positive sequence

Normally, when there are done dynamic analysis of VSCs, is done the linear model with only positive sequence, even though, in practice, VSCs have positive and negative sequences control. The objective is to see if the addition of this negative sequence control is relevant to the studies or if it can be neglected. To do that, it has been firstly obtained a linear model of the system with only positive sequence. As shown in Figures 30, 31 and 32, it has been validated that the model used is correctly linearized by changing the active and reactive reference powers at $t=2$ s.

Figure 30: dq-currents with the positive sequence non-linear system and changing powers references.

Figure 31: qd-voltages with the positive sequence non-linear system and changing powers references.

Figure 32: Angular velocity with the positive sequence non-linear system and changing power references.

It is concluded that the created linear model is a good approximation of the non-linear model with only a positive sequence.

6.2 abc-abc* validation

Before validating the linear model obtained with positive and negative sequence control, a simple verification has been done to prove that the presented methodology always loses information when the negative sequence appears. The test that has been done takes a signal in abc frame,

obtains their qd^{+-} values and after that, the abc frame values are obtained again, as shown in Figure 33.

Figure 33: abc-abc* validation.

If this test is done when qd or $\alpha\beta$ sequence values are obtained, the abc frame values will be the same in both cases. However, with qd^{+-} sequence, Figure 34 shows the difference between voltages before the conversion and after the conversion, changing phase a at $t=0.5$ s and phase b at $t=1$ s.

Figure 34: Difference between initial and final abc values.

From the obtained results it is clear that when there are unbalances, both signals have different values, although supposedly both signals have to have the same value. abc signal is multiplied only by the Park transform, the filter and the Inverse Park transform. The Park transform and its Inverse, as its name says, are inverse matrices, so they do not add any dynamics to the signal. So, it is clear that this difference comes from the filter. One possible idea to reduce this error, at least with the non-linear model is using another type of filter to delete the second-order harmonics. So, a FIR filter as the one in Section 3 is used. The same test as before is done obtaining the results shown in Figure 35.

Figure 35: Difference between initial and final abc values.

From the obtained results it can be seen that the results are faster than in the case of the designed filter in Section 4.2.3 but with a bigger amplitude. However, if this filter is linearized, it is required to use again a Padé filter, which will delete the mentioned velocity. Therefore, the notch filter is used during all the studied cases.

Finally, to see the effect of the filter, it is also studied a case in which the three abc phases are changed at $t=0.5$ s. This experiment shown at Figure 36, could represent what happens if it is changed the reference value of the positive current.

Figure 36: Difference between initial and final abc values.

From the test developed in this Section, it is seen that the dynamics that appear due to the filter cannot be deleted. Knowing also that there appear signals before the filters at 100 Hz, it is proven that with the methodology presented in this article, the linear model cannot be improved more. So, in the following Sections, some tests are done with the non-linear models to analyse in different conditions how critical are the errors and if they can be dismissed.

6.3 Non-linear coupled system

In VSCs with positive and negative sequence control, it is used a filter to calculate from the grid voltage, each of the sequences. In practice, the coupling, and therefore the filter, will introduce some dynamics, as it is explained in Section 4.2.3. For this reason, this Section aims to analyse

the model with the filter. The problem that the author has found doing this procedure is the coupling of positive and negative grid voltages and currents. As the linear models of each sequence are done in qd^{+-} , the inputs of the filter are (Section 3.1):

$$F_1 = u^{q+} + e^{-2j\omega t} u^{q-}, \quad (99)$$

$$F_2 = u^{d+} + e^{-2j\omega t} u^{d-}, \quad (100)$$

$$F_3 = u^{q-} + e^{-2j\omega t} u^{q+}, \quad (101)$$

$$F_4 = u^{d-} + e^{-2j\omega t} u^{d+}. \quad (102)$$

where F_1 , F_2 , F_3 and F_4 are the inputs of the filters. All these calculations are also extrapolated to the currents. Therefore, the results between the non-linear and the linear model will vary, because the linear model cannot take into account this coupling at different frequencies. It is for this reason, that in the literature, the results obtained are always ensuring MFD [6, 7], as if MFD property is accomplished, it is ensured in steady state that the sequences are decoupled between them. However, these studies do not consider the transients. Therefore in this thesis the results are shown in temporal domain.

6.3.1 Powers variation

The active and reactive powers are changed to a value of 1% at $t=2$ s. Figures 37, 38 and 39 show the comparison between the non-linear and the linear model.

(a) Positive currents.

(b) Negative currents.

Figure 37: Currents validation with the coupled non-linear system and changing powers references.

(a) Positive voltages.

(b) Negative voltages.

Figure 38: Voltages validation with the coupled non-linear system and changing powers references.

Figure 39: Angular velocities validation with the coupled non-linear system and changing powers references.

Due to the change in the amplitude of the filtered 100 Hz q^+ and d^+ signals when the power is changed (the signal remains at 0 but this change has an effect), the linear model does not behave as the non-linear model. As has been mentioned, the problem is that it is not taken into account the coupling between the positive and negative voltages and currents at 100 Hz. So, it is clear that with this scenario and the presented methodology would not be possible to obtain an identical linear model. However, the error of the variables that are near 0 at steady state are small compared the other cases. The cases where the variables are not near 0, have more oscillations, which are similar to the ones that appear at the non-linear model near 0. In conclusion, even the coupling is not taken into account, there is an effect at the linear model of the negative currents oscillations at the positive currents oscillations. In Section 7 are analysed different cases to see if the error between the nonlinear and the linear model could be belittled.

6.3.2 Voltage variation

Although it is clear with the change of powers that this model is not catching all the dynamics of the non-linear model, a test with an unbalancing at phase a has also been done, to see the behaviour when the negative sequence appears. From Section 3.1.4 it is seen that if phase a changes 1% its nominal value, q^+ and q^- change their values $\frac{1}{3} \cdot 0.01$ its nominal value. d^+ and d^- remain 0.

(a) Positive currents.

(b) Negative currents.

Figure 40: Currents validation with the coupled non-linear system and changing phase a .

(a) Positive voltages.

(b) Negative voltages.

Figure 41: Voltages validation with the coupled non-linear system and changing phase a .

Figure 42: Angular velocities validation with the coupled non-linear system and changing phase a .

Analyzing the results it is shown that again there are not caught all the dynamics in the transient. In this case, only the positive and negative voltages in the q component have behaviour as desired. As it happened before, it can be concluded that due to the coupling in 100 Hz frequency, all the dynamics cannot be caught.

6.4 Non-linear uncoupled system

With the interpretation of qd^{+-} obtained in Section 3, it can be concluded that if there are used two grids, one for each sequence (+ and -), it is only required to rotate $2\pi 50t$ or $-2\pi 50t$ the obtained voltages and currents at the point of common coupling (PCC), which simplifies the linearization of the system as a filter is not required. So, in this Section, it is considered that the non-linear model is uncoupled [20, 24], as Figure 28 shows, so the linear model created is compared. In this case, the filter is still taken into account (although is not necessary) to try to be as realistic as possible.

6.4.1 Powers variation

Firstly, to validate the linear model obtained, the results between the non-linear model and the linear model are compared. In this case, there are changed the nominal values of active and reactive power 1% of its nominal value at $t=2s$.

(a) Positive currents.

(b) Negative currents.

Figure 43: Currents validation with the uncoupled non-linear system and changing powers references.

(a) Positive voltages.

(b) Negative voltages.

Figure 44: Voltages validation with the uncoupled non-linear system and changing powers references.

Figure 45: Angular velocities validation with the uncoupled non-linear system and changing powers references.

The results show that in this case, the linear model catches all the dynamics of the non-linear uncoupled model (Figure 28). Also, the negative voltages and currents can be considered 0 during the simulation, as there are no unbalances.

6.4.2 Voltage variation

To validate the negative sequence behaviour of the linear model is changed the voltage, specifically the phase a of the voltage of the grid. The value has been changed 1% its nominal value at $t=2$ s, creating also an unbalancing as phase a is bigger than phases b and c . The results obtained are:

(a) Positive currents.

(b) Negative currents.

Figure 46: Currents validation with the uncoupled non-linear system and changing phase a .

(a) Positive voltages.

(b) Negative voltages.

Figure 47: Voltages validation with the uncoupled non-linear system and changing phase a .

Figure 48: Angular velocities validation with the uncoupled non-linear system and changing phase a .

In this case, both models have the same dynamics too. Also, it can be seen that in the negative sequence case, after the changing of phase a , the voltages change their values so that the unbalancing can be controlled. The obtained linear model represents a system in which is not considered the coupling between voltages and currents. However, it is known that in practice, the signals are coupled, so the following section analyses the non-linear coupled model (Figure 27) in different scenarios to see if the differences between the obtained linear model and the non-linear coupled model are small enough to be dismissed.

7 Non-linear coupled model analysis

In this Section, the non-linear coupled model is analysed in more detail versus the linear model, to see how important is the error of not taking into account the coupling. The following scenarios are studied:

- Ideal grid.
- Weak grid.
- MFD system.

7.1 Ideal grid

The first scenario is the case in which it is considered that the grid is ideal ($SCR=\infty$) so that there are no resistances and inductances in the grid (the coupling resistances and inductances still exist). The hypothesis of an ideal grid is typical in small-signal analysis [25], so it has been taken into account also in this thesis. Applying this supposition is as applying the variables R_{eq} and L_{eq} as 0. The results are being studied when there is a variation in the reference active and reactive power or when there is a change in the grid reference voltage, specifically phase a .

7.1.1 Powers variation

The results with the powers reference variation are:

(a) Positive currents.

(b) Negative currents.

Figure 49: Currents on the ideal grid case changing reference powers.

(a) Positive voltages.

(b) Negative voltages.

Figure 50: Voltages on the ideal grid case changing reference powers.

Figure 51: Angular velocities on the ideal grid case changing reference powers.

From the results obtained it can be seen that due to the ideal grid, all the variables are constant except the currents. Because of the change in the references, the currents vary, so the undesired transient dynamics appear too.

7.1.2 Voltage variation

The results with phase a variation are:

(a) Positive currents.

(b) Negative currents.

Figure 52: Currents on the ideal grid case changing phase a .

(a) Positive voltages.

(b) Negative voltages.

Figure 53: Voltages on the ideal grid case changing phase a .Figure 54: Angular velocities on the ideal grid case changing phase a .

The results obtained are similar to the ones with the original grid (strong grid), as Section 6.3 shows.

7.2 Weak grid

A weak grid could be defined as a grid with a low SCR, in the case of this scenario it is going to be used a $SCR = 3$ [26]. As it has been done in the ideal grid case, tests are done by changing the power references and the phase a of the grid voltage.

7.2.1 Powers variation

When the references of the powers have a variation the results obtained are:

(a) Positive currents.

(b) Negative currents.

Figure 55: Currents on the weak grid case changing reference powers.

(a) Positive voltages.

(b) Negative voltages.

Figure 56: Voltages on the weak grid case changing reference powers.

Figure 57: Angular velocities on the weak grid case changing reference powers.

When the references are changed, it is seen that because of the not coupling of the signals, the negative currents and voltages still do not have variation in the linear model, whereas this variation exists in the non-linear model. In this case, the magnitude of the error is even bigger, because the non-linear model has a bigger oscillation. Also, the q component of the voltage has a variation in the steady state, but this small error is a consequence of the high non-linearity of the non-linear model [26].

7.2.2 Voltage variation

If the a phase of the grid voltage is changed:

(a) Positive currents.

(b) Negative currents.

Figure 58: Currents on the weak grid case changing phase a .

(a) Positive voltages.

(b) Negative voltages.

Figure 59: Voltages on the weak grid case changing phase a .Figure 60: Angular velocities on the weak grid case changing phase a .

Analyzing the results obtained when phase a is changed, it is concluded that these are the results with the biggest variation between both models. However, the biggest variation between both cases is about 114% of its value (I_q^-), and the difference in magnitude is 6.047 A. This effect happens in a peak value (produced by the filtering of a sinusoidal signal of 100 Hz), and after that, the errors are always smaller, although, in the steady state, the positive signals still have the same variation due to the high non-linearities that the weak grid produce.

So, with a weak grid, the error is bigger, mainly due to the non-linearity of the system but still can be considered acceptable.

7.3 Mirror Frequency Decomposition system

From the studies that have been done in the literature about linear models of a VSC with positive and negative sequence control [6, 7], it is seen that it is common to study MFD systems, so it can be considered that the coupling between positive and negative sequence in stationary state is 0. However, these publications have been done in the frequency range and without taking into account the fact that there will always be a coupling at 100 Hz between positive and negative sequences during the transients in the filter. So, in this section, there are done all the required arrangements to ensure that the studied system is MFD and it is analysed in the temporal domain how are the results. To define the system as MFD it is necessary that the positive and negative sequence control are symmetrical and that there are accomplished the conditions presented on [7]. So the following changes are done:

- The grid is ideal.
- There is no PLL, the frequency is directly $2\pi 50$.
- The outer loop power control is deleted and only remain the dynamics of the inner current loop. To calculate the positive current references are directly used the reference active and reactive powers and the nominal value of the voltage of the grid.

With these changes, it is ensured that the model is MFD [6, 7], so the results obtained when there is a change of the active and reactive power references are shown in Figures 61 and 62.

(a) Positive currents.

(b) Negative currents.

Figure 61: Currents on the MFD case.

(a) Positive voltages.

(b) Negative voltages.

Figure 62: Voltages on the MFD case.

Figures 61 and 62 demonstrate that in this case, the voltages are not affected by the change of the

power reference, as expected. However, as the reference positive current is changed and there is the coupling in 100 Hz at the negative current, this effect makes the behaviour of the linear and the non-linear model different. This different behaviour is also reproduced in the positive current at 100 Hz, making a different transient. So, it can be seen that until 0.1 s the dynamics of the current are not correctly caught due to the effect of the coupling and the filter. So, even if the system is MFD, there will always exist a difference between the linear and the non-linear model if the coupling at 100 Hz is not taken into account.

From all the different testings, it has been arrived at the conclusion that it is clear that with the presented methodology in this thesis is not taken into account the coupling and therefore the results are different. However, as the error is low and it mainly affects fast dynamics, a dynamic analysis of the linear model is done.

8 Eigenvalues analysis

Another objective of this thesis is to do a dynamic analysis to check how is the behaviour of the model with positive and negative sequence control. As the linear model obtained in Section 6.1 is considered to be good enough, even if it is not coupled, a dynamic analysis is done with the same parameters defined in Section 6.

8.1 Eigenvalues comparison between models with positive sequence control and positive and negative sequence control

Both linear model eigenvalues are compared in Figure 63.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 63: Eigenvalues of the linear models.

In Figure 63a seems that both systems have almost the same eigenvalue locations. However, if the eigenvalues near the positive real values are analysed, Figure 63b shows that there are more eigenvalues in the linear model with both sequences as they appear near one positive sequence model pole, two more eigenvalues at right and left. They are very close eigenvalues, so, they will not have a significant impact on the dynamics of the linear model with only positive sequence.

If it is zoomed the plot near 0, as Figure 63c shows, it is seen that the system with positive and

negative sequences has more eigenvalues, especially where the real part is -60. These added eigenvalues are a direct consequence of the filters, and if they are analyzed it can be seen that as there are added four 2nd order filters, there are added these 8 eigenvalues which are conjugated. Table 1 shows a summary of how is the damping ratio and frequency of these conjugated added eigenvalues by the filter.

Pole	Damping ratio	Frequency [Hz]
$-59.91 \pm j524.932$	0.1134	83.55
$-59.54 \pm j333.214$	0.1758	53.03
$-59.09 \pm j526.091$	0.1116	83.73
$-62.85 \pm j329.302$	0.1875	52.41

Table 1: Frequency and damping ratio of the added eigenvalues in the positive and negative sequence model.

Also, a pole appears near 0, which is related to the negative sequence control. This pole as will be shown later is static in all the operation eigenvalues.

From the analysis done in this section, it could be concluded that even it is done the simplification that the grids are uncoupled, the linear model with positive and negative sequence control does not add an important difference with the model with only positive sequence control, so it can be used the model with only one sequence.

8.2 Pole analysis at different operation points

Finally, it is analyzed the linear model in different operation points to see how the eigenvalues change between them. There have been studied two scenarios:

- Maintain all the variables and change the active power reference.
- Maintain all the variables and change the reactive power reference.
- Maintain all the variables and change the negative current references.

8.2.1 Active power reference

As the converter studied has a nominal power of 300 kVA, it will be studied the eigenvalues in the following scenarios:

- $P^*=0$ kW.
- $P^*=50$ kW.
- $P^*=100$ kW.
- $P^*=200$ kW.

It is important to remember that the reactive power is maintained constant in this case study, so it will always be 100 kVar. The eigenvalues in each of the cases are shown in Figures 64a and 64b

(a)

(b)

Figure 64: eigenvalues of the linear system with different active power references.

From the results, it is seen that at all the possible operation points of the active power reference,

the converter is stable. Also, the bigger the active power, the more stable the converter.

8.2.2 Reactive power reference

In this section, there are analysed different reactive power references maintaining all the other parameters constant. The operation points that are studied are:

- $Q^*=0$ kVA.
- $Q^*=50$ kVA.
- $Q^*=100$ kVA.

Figures 65a and 65b show the obtained eigenvalues.

(a)

Figure 65: eigenvalues of the linear system with different reactive power references.

Again, it is ensured that the converter will be stable for all the possible operation points. As it happened with the active power reference, there is more stability for bigger reactive power references.

8.2.3 Negative current reference

Finally, to see how it affects the negative sequence in the system, the following operating points are studied:

- $I_q^{*-} = 0$ A.
- $I_q^{*-} = 10$ A.
- $I_q^{*-} = 40$ A.
- $I_q^{*-} = 400$ A.

(a)

(b)

Figure 66: eigenvalues of the linear system with different negative current references.

As can be seen in Figure 66, the change of negative current reference does not have an important

effect on the system, as all the eigenvalues are stable and almost the same.

9 Schedule

As this thesis represents a total amount of 24 ECTS and one ECTS is 25 hours, at least there has to be done 600 h of work. The research of this thesis was started in March 2023, as it was when the author started reading the literature about positive and negative sequences. To organize all the work that the author had to do and to ensure that the other research paths were not stopped, a Gantt Chart was made.

The initial idea was that each day, the author would invest 2 hours on this thesis. During the summer holidays (23 days) he did not schedule work time. Also, during the Christmas holidays the author supposed that he would need to make more hours, so he scheduled 8 hours/day (except the 25th and 26th of December and the 1st and 6th of January, which I did not schedule work). This means that in total the author calculated that he would do 628 hours and end the thesis on the 7th of January, as shown in Figure 67.

Figure 67: Gantt chart planned.

However, it is known that all projects have setbacks, so it was decided to make a control of hours, to compare if the times were the same that were calculated at the start of the project. With this control of hours made, it was generated another Gantt chart, making easier the comparison.

Figure 68: Real hours Gantt chart.

As can be seen in Figure 68 due to different reasons, the author invested more than the expected time at the beginning and end of the project. On the other hand, after the summer holidays, the author did not invest a lot of time in the thesis. The total hours that he invested in this thesis are 840 h, which it is seen that is more than what was initially expected. The main reasons were the review of the literature, which was longer than calculated and the building of the linear model for the VSC with positive and negative sequence control and a filter was very challenging, as the author made an extensive literature revision and made a lot of different tests to try to couple the voltages and currents with the actual methodology.

10 Budget

As it is explained in Section 9, there were worked 840 hours at the moment that this thesis was finished. The income that the author receives for doing research is 11.17 €/h [27], so the personal cost of this thesis was 9382.8 €.

Also, this thesis needs to have a Matlab license to do all the simulations and a powerful computer that could afford them, as some require an important computation time. However, both tools were not only used for this thesis, as they were also used in other projects, so all the costs have been multiplied by a correction factor which depended on the days that I used each tool.

Matlab Academic license costs 262 €/year [28]. I have been working 223 days this year, which means that I worked 1784 h. Knowing that I invested in this thesis 840 h, and due to the large computation time required for the simulations, it can be considered that I have been all the thesis using Matlab-Simulink. So, the cost that the Matlab license represents is:

$$262[\text{€/year}] * \frac{840[h]}{1784[h/\text{year}]} = 123.36[\text{€}] \quad (103)$$

On the other hand, I have been using a Dell Vostro 15 5510, which costs 600 € [29]. Assuming that the use of the computer would be about 5 years, it could be done again the calculation of the cost of the computer in this project:

$$600[\text{€}] * \frac{840[h]}{5[\text{years}] * 1784[h/\text{year}]} = 56.5[\text{€}] \quad (104)$$

The last cost is the cost of the energy that has been required to use the computer. The Dell Vostro 15 has a power of 15 W [29]. So, the energy used is:

$$15[W] * 840[h] = 12600[Wh] \quad (105)$$

Considering that the medium price of energy in Catalonia is 0.2 €/kWh [30], the energy cost is:

$$12.6[kWh] * \frac{0.2[\text{€}]}{1[kWh]} = 2.52[\text{€}] \quad (106)$$

To sum up, the total costs of this project have been:

Type of cost	Hours [h]	Price/hour [€/h]	Cost [€]
Personal cost	840	11.17	9382.8
Matlab license	840	0.1469	123.36
Computer amortization	840	0.067	56.5
Energy consumption	840	-	2.52
Total	840		9565.18

Table 2: Table with the costs.

11 Environmental impact

The environmental impact of this thesis is not an easy calculation. First, it is important to remark that as the nature of this project is theoretical, the results' value is the knowledge they give, as they are not applied in a specific case. So, the only real environmental impact that this thesis has is the CO_2 that has been produced by the energy used by the computer. In Section 10 it is shown that the computer wasted 12600 Wh during the project.

In Catalonia, the CO_2 emitted by kWh produced is 259 gCO_2/kWh [31]. Considering that the efficiency of the energy produced will be for sure a value lower than 1, it can be said that at least the CO_2 produced by this thesis is:

$$259[gCO_2/kWh] * \frac{1[kWh]}{1000[Wh]} * 12600[Wh] = 3263.4[gCO_2] = 3.263[kgCO_2] \quad (107)$$

On the other hand, the summary of sequences in Section 3 and the linear model in Section 6.4 could be useful for people who want to implement them in the control of converters or who want to use their properties for other studies like passivity, which could simplify some calculations. Thanks to these contributions, it could be reduced the production of greenhouse gases and the use of non-renewable sources like coal or gas [32].

However, the increase in the use of these technologies causes an increase in the production of elements like lithium or semiconductors, which are being each time more scarce [33]. Apart from that, if there are installed renewable generation sources, each of them requires a precise environmental study, as they could have an important effect on the earth. For example, wind generation could produce important problems for birds and their migrations [34].

So, the objective of the author is that this thesis has a positive environmental impact, but it will depend on how will be used the information given in this thesis.

12 Social analysis and gender perspective

To analyze the social impact of the thesis, it has been decided to check the UN's Sustainable Development Goals and analyze if some are accomplished [35]. It has been concluded that the following ones are being treated by this thesis:

- Goal 7: Affordable and clean energy.
- Goal 9: Industry, innovation and infrastructure.
- Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities.

These 3 goals are related to this thesis and many of their targets and indicators could be associated with the contribution given by this document. So, in terms of sustainability and social wellness, it can be considered that the output obtained by this thesis has a positive social impact. Also, the fact that this report is uploaded as open-source could be considered a good impact, as everybody who has internet could access the information given, obtaining in this way that the knowledge becomes open and free.

On the other hand, the gender perspective of this thesis is limited, as the author and directors are males and there is not a clear application that could help with gender equality. However, there can be done some interesting annotations related to this work.

First, as this project has been done in a research centre from UPC, I have been more in contact than when I was a student with research personnel and I observed that the ratio between both genders is not balanced, as Figure 69 shows.

Figure 69: Research personnel in UPC by position, category and gender. Source [36].

UPC is trying to reduce this gap, but it is clear that the effort has to be maintained or even upgraded.

Second, I also want to dedicate some lines to Edith Clarke [37]. She was the woman who found what is known today as the Clarke transformation, widely used in power electronics. I discov-

ered her story while reviewing the literature and it was a learning experience. Even though she was exceptional as an engineer, she could not work as an electrical engineer until she was 39 years old and after a lot of discoveries like the Clarke calculator [38] or the Clarke transformation [39]. Nowadays this story seems far, but there is still discrimination around the world, so it is still important to learn about these stories and try to have the most equality possible, as, in the end, society will benefit.

Conclusions and Future Work

This thesis has made a detailed explanation of how to calculate positive and negative sequences for VSCs and how to understand them. Also has been proposed unified criteria to understand which are the different components that are obtained when Fortescue, Forward-Backward and Complex-Real transformations are applied. From these calculations, it also has been obtained the equations that relate in steady state abc frame with positive and negative sequences components, more specifically in qd^{+-} frame. With all this information the author understands that the first objective of the thesis has been accomplished.

The remaining objectives of the thesis were to see if it is possible to make a linear model considering qd^{+-} and analyse their importance compared with a model with only a positive sequence. To accomplish this objective there have been studied the models taking into account two hypotheses: that the positive and negative grids are coupled or not.

Due to the impossibility of coupling voltages and currents, it has been seen that the linear model could not catch all the dynamics of the non-linear coupled model, especially the fast ones. It has also been detected by the author that the problem is that in the non-linear coupled model, the coupling between voltages and currents has components at 0 Hz and 100 Hz. So, it has been seen that with the presented methodology, an exact solution with the filter and the coupling is not possible, even if the system is MFD. However, in Section 7 it has been proven that the error between the linear model and the non-linear coupled model is small, and it only exists in the fast dynamics of the transient.

In the case that it is considered that there is no interaction between positive and negative voltages and currents, the linear model created fully describes the non-linear dynamics.

With the linear model, it also has been seen that there are differences in the eigenvalues with respect to the model with only positive sequence, but they can be neglected, as they have a small impact on the dynamics. Also, if the operation points are changed, the results remain quite similar. So, it has been seen that the presented model is an improvement to the linear models that only take into account positive sequence, but the effect is so small, that there can be done the small signal analysis directly with only positive sequence control.

To conclude, this thesis explained the qd^{+-} sequences and their obtention and it has been seen that they can be neglected when linear analysis are done. Furthermore, it has been detected that with the presented methodology is not possible to take into account all the dynamics of the coupling between voltages and currents.

With the work done in this thesis, the idea is to keep doing research on how to catch the dynamics of the coupling. One possibility is to analyse if the dynamics that appear at the linear models in its positive sequences can be related in some way to the dynamics of the negative sequences and vice-versa. Another option is the study of multifrequency models, which define a linear model in multiple frequencies. This idea has not been applied at this thesis because the required time to create these models is too significant. Apart from these studies, the author will write a conference paper to explain the obtained results in this thesis, to try to help with the understanding of positive and negative sequences.

Thanks

Thanks to Marc, Robert and Oriol, for all the good advice and thanks to all my other colleagues from CITCEA-UPC for helping me to discover the research world.

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Finally, thanks to the reader for being interested in this report and I hope for enjoy it.

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Appendix A: Linear modelling of the VSC with Matlab

The codes to create the linear model with Matlab are shown in this appendix. The code first takes the steady state values obtained with *trimming* function. Once these values are known, there are build each of the parts of the linear model and connected. The obtained model is simulated and validated with Simulink.

12.1 Linear model with only positive sequence

```
1 index=29009;
2
3 Vq_c_0=out.Vq_VSC_ss(index);
4 Iq_c_0=out.Iq_vsc_ss(index);
5
6 Vq_c_2=out.Vq_VSC_ss2(index);
7 Iq_c_2=out.Iq_vsc_ss2(index);
8
9
10
11
12
13 Vd_c_0=out.Vd_VSC_ss(index);
14 Id_c_0=out.Id_vsc_ss(index);
15
16
17
18 Vd_c_2=out.Vd_VSC_ss2(index);
19 Id_c_2=out.Id_vsc_ss2(index);
20
21
22
23
24
25
26 P_0=out.Pref(index);
27 Q_0=out.Qref(index);
28
29 e_theta_0=out.e_theta(index);
30
31
32
33 Uq_c_0=getdatasamples(out.Uq_cc,index);
34 Ud_c_0=getdatasamples(out.Ud_cc,index);
35
36
37 omega_0=out.omega_pll(index);
38
39
40 Iq_ref_0=out.iqref(index);
```

```

41 Id_ref_0=out.idref(index);
42
43
44
45
46 %% u to uc rotating to qd values to grid reference
47
48 A_rot_uc=[0];
49 B_rot_uc=[0 0 0];
50 C_rot_uc=[0;0];
51 D_rot_uc=[cos(e_theta_0) -sin(e_theta_0) -sin(e_theta_0)*Vq_c_0-cos
(e_theta_0)*Vd_c_0;
52     sin(e_theta_0) cos(e_theta_0) cos(e_theta_0)*Vq_c_0-sin(
e_theta_0)*Vd_c_0];
53 rot_uc_x={' '};
54 rot_uc_u={'Uq_pll','Ud_pll','e_theta'};
55 rot_uc_y={'Uq_pos_c','Ud_pos_c'};
56 rot_uc= ss(A_rot_uc,B_rot_uc,C_rot_uc,D_rot_uc,'StateName',rot_uc_x
,'inputname',rot_uc_u,'outputname',rot_uc_y);
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64 %% i to ic rotating to qd values to converter reference
65
66 A_rot_ic=[0];
67 B_rot_ic=[0 0 0];
68 C_rot_ic=[0;0];
69 D_rot_ic=[cos(e_theta_0) -sin(e_theta_0) -sin(e_theta_0)*Iq_c_0-cos
(e_theta_0)*Id_c_0;
70     sin(e_theta_0) cos(e_theta_0) cos(e_theta_0)*Iq_c_0-sin(
e_theta_0)*Id_c_0];
71 rot_ic_x={' '};
72 rot_ic_u={'is_q','is_d','e_theta'};
73 rot_ic_y={'Iq_pos_c','Id_pos_c'};
74 rot_ic= ss(A_rot_ic,B_rot_ic,C_rot_ic,D_rot_ic,'StateName',rot_ic_x
,'inputname',rot_ic_u,'outputname',rot_ic_y);
75
76
77
78
79 %% vcc to vc reserve transform
80
81 A_rot_vcc=[0];
82 B_rot_vcc=[0 0 0];
83 C_rot_vcc=[0;0];

```

```

84 D_rot_vcc=[cos(e_theta_0) sin(e_theta_0) -sin(e_theta_0)*Uq_c_0+cos
      (e_theta_0)*Ud_c_0;
85      -sin(e_theta_0) cos(e_theta_0) -cos(e_theta_0)*Uq_c_0-sin(
      e_theta_0)*Ud_c_0];
86 rot_vcc_x={' '};
87 rot_vcc_u={'Uq_c','Ud_c','e_theta'};
88 rot_vcc_y={'Vq_cc','Vd_cc'};
89 rot_vcc= ss(A_rot_vcc,B_rot_vcc,C_rot_vcc,D_rot_vcc,'StateName',
      rot_vcc_x,'inputname',rot_vcc_u,'outputname',rot_vcc_y);
90
91
92
93 %% P control
94
95 A_p_cont=[0];
96 B_p_cont=[0 0]; % I define Pref-Pmeas
97 C_p_cont=[0];
98 D_p_cont=[2/(3*Vq_c_0) 2/3*(-P_0/Vq_c_0^2)];
99 p_cont_x={' '};
100 p_cont_u={'Pref' 'Uq_pos_c'};
101 p_cont_y={'Iq_ref'};
102 p_cont = ss(A_p_cont,B_p_cont,C_p_cont,D_p_cont,'StateName',
      p_cont_x,'inputname',p_cont_u,'outputname',p_cont_y);
103
104 %% Q control
105
106 A_q_cont=[0];
107 B_q_cont=[0 0];
108 C_q_cont=[0];
109 D_q_cont=[2/(3*Vq_c_0) 2/3*(-Q_0/Vq_c_0^2)];
110 q_cont_x={' '};
111 q_cont_u={'Qref' 'Uq_pos_c'};
112 q_cont_y={'Id_ref'};
113 q_cont = ss(A_q_cont,B_q_cont,C_q_cont,D_q_cont,'StateName',
      q_cont_x,'inputname',q_cont_u,'outputname',q_cont_y);
114
115
116
117
118 %% Current control
119 w1=2*pi*50;
120 A_cc=[0 0;0 0];
121 B_cc=[1 0 -1 0 0 0;
122       0 1 0 -1 0 0];
123 C_cc=[-Ki_cl_1 0;
124       0 -Ki_cl_1];
125 D_cc=[-Kp_cl_1 0 Kp_cl_1 -w1*Ll_1 1 0;
126       0 -Kp_cl_1 w1*Ll_1 Kp_cl_1 0 1];
127 cc_x={'Ki_q_cc','Ki_d_cc'};

```

```

128 cc_u={'Iq_ref','Id_ref','Iq_pos_c','Id_pos_c','Uq_pos_c','Ud_pos_c'
      }; % 'Vq_VSC','Vd_VSC','Iq_VSC','Id_VSC' will come from the
      conversion matrixes
129 cc_y={'Uq_c_d','Ud_c_d'};
130 cc = ss(A_cc,B_cc,C_cc,D_cc,'StateName',cc_x,'inputname',cc_u,'
      outputname',cc_y);
131
132 %% Delay
133 [num,den]=pade(1e-4,20);
134 [A_d,B_d,C_d,D_d]=tf2ss(num,den);
135 d_x={'state_delay'};
136 d_u={'Uq_c_d'};
137 d_y={'Uq_c'};
138 d_1=ss(A_d,B_d,C_d,D_d,'inputname',d_u,'outputname',d_y);
139 d_x={'state_delay2'};
140 d_u={'Ud_c_d'};
141 d_y={'Ud_c'};
142 d_2=ss(A_d,B_d,C_d,D_d,'inputname',d_u,'outputname',d_y);
143
144
145
146 %% PLL
147
148 A_pll=[0];
149 B_pll=[1];
150 C_pll=[-Ki_pll_1];
151 D_pll=[-Kp_pll_1];
152 pll_x={'Ki_PLL'};
153 pll_u={'Ud_pos_c'};
154 pll_y={'omega_PLL'};
155 pll = ss(A_pll,B_pll,C_pll,D_pll,'StateName',pll_x,'inputname',
      pll_u,'outputname',pll_y);
156
157
158
159 %% e theta (PLL-grid for rotating to converters reference)
160
161 A_theta=[0];
162 B_theta=[1 -1];
163 C_theta=[1];
164 D_theta=[0 0];
165 theta_x={'e_theta'};
166 theta_u={'omega_PLL','omega'};
167 theta_y={'e_theta'};
168 theta= ss(A_theta,B_theta,C_theta,D_theta,'StateName',theta_x,'
      inputname',theta_u,'outputname',theta_y);
169
170
171

```

```

172 % Converter
173
174 R_tr=Req_1;
175 L_tr=Leq_1;
176 A_vsc=[-(Req_1+Rl_1)/(Leq_1+Ll_1) -w1;
177         w1 -(Req_1+Rl_1)/(Leq_1+Ll_1)];
178 B_vsc=[-1/(Leq_1+Ll_1) 0 1/(Leq_1+Ll_1) 0; 0 -1/(Leq_1+Ll_1) 0 1/(
179         Leq_1+Ll_1)];
179 C_vsc=[1 0;
180        0 1;
181        (-R_tr+L_tr*(Rl_1+R_tr)/(Ll_1+L_tr)) 0;
182        0 (-R_tr+L_tr*(Rl_1+R_tr)/(Ll_1+L_tr))];
183 D_vsc=[0 0 0 0;
184        0 0 0 0;
185        L_tr/(Ll_1+L_tr) 0 (1-L_tr/(Ll_1+L_tr)) 0;
186        0 L_tr/(Ll_1+L_tr) 0 (1-L_tr/(Ll_1+L_tr))];
187 vsc_x={'is_q' 'is_d'};
188 vsc_u={'Vq_cc' 'Vd_cc' 'Uq_TH' 'Ud_TH' };
189 vsc_y={'is_q' 'is_d' 'Uq_pll' 'Ud_pll'};
190 vsc = ss(A_vsc,B_vsc,C_vsc,D_vsc,'StateName',vsc_x,'inputname',
191         vsc_u,'outputname',vsc_y);
192
193 %% Total model
194
195 VSC_total_pi = connect(d_1,d_2,rot_vcc,rot_ic,rot_uc,p_cont,q_cont,
196         cc,pll,theta,vsc,["Pref","Qref","Uq_TH", "Ud_TH", "omega"],{'
197         Iq_pos_c','Id_pos_c','Uq_pos_c','Ud_pos_c','omega_PLL','Iq_ref',
198         'Id_ref'});

```

12.2 Linear model with positive and negative sequences

```

1     index=29009;
2
3     Vq_c_0=out.Vq_VSC_ss(index);
4     Iq_c_0=out.Iq_vsc_ss(index);
5
6     Vq_c_1=out.Vq_VSC_ss1(index);
7     Iq_c_1=out.Iq_vsc_ss1(index);
8
9     Vq_c_2=out.Vq_VSC_ss2(index);
10    Iq_c_2=out.Iq_vsc_ss2(index);
11
12    Vq_c_3=out.Vq_VSC_ss3(index);
13    Iq_c_3=out.Iq_vsc_ss3(index);
14
15
16    Vd_c_0=out.Vd_VSC_ss(index);
17    Id_c_0=out.Id_vsc_ss(index);

```

```

18
19 Vd_c_1=out.Vd_VSC_ss1(index);
20 Id_c_1=out.Id_vsc_ss1(index);
21
22 Vd_c_2=out.Vd_VSC_ss2(index);
23 Id_c_2=out.Id_vsc_ss2(index);
24
25 Vd_c_3=out.Vd_VSC_ss3(index);
26 Id_c_3=out.Id_vsc_ss3(index);
27
28
29
30 P_0=out.Pref(index);
31 Q_0=out.Qref(index);
32
33 e_theta_0=out.e_theta(index);
34 e_theta_1=out.e_theta1(index);
35
36 Uq_c_0=getdatasamples(out.Uq_cc,index);
37 Ud_c_0=getdatasamples(out.Ud_cc,index);
38
39 Uq_c_1=getdatasamples(out.Uq_cc1,index);
40 Ud_c_1=getdatasamples(out.Ud_cc1,index);
41
42
43 omega_0=out.omega_pll(index);
44 omega_1=out.omega_pll1(index);
45
46
47 Iq_ref_0=out.iqref(index);
48 Id_ref_0=out.idref(index);
49 Iq_ref_1=out.iqref1(index);
50 Id_ref_1=out.idref1(index);
51
52
53 %% u to uc rotating to qd values to grid reference
54
55 A_rot_uc=[0];
56 B_rot_uc=[0 0 0];
57 C_rot_uc=[0;0];
58 D_rot_uc=[cos(e_theta_0) -sin(e_theta_0) -sin(e_theta_0)*Vq_c_0-cos
    (e_theta_0)*Vd_c_0;
59     sin(e_theta_0) cos(e_theta_0) cos(e_theta_0)*Vq_c_0-sin(
    e_theta_0)*Vd_c_0];
60 rot_uc_x={' '};
61 rot_uc_u={'Uq_pll','Ud_pll','e_theta'};
62 rot_uc_y={'Vq_c','Vd_c'};
63 rot_uc= ss(A_rot_uc,B_rot_uc,C_rot_uc,D_rot_uc,'StateName',rot_uc_x
    , 'inputname',rot_uc_u,'outputname',rot_uc_y);

```

```

64
65 %% Filter
66 clear tf
67 filter=tf([1,-4*100*pi,(2*100*pi)^2],[1,4*100*pi,(2*100*pi)^2]);
68 matrix=[1/2*(1+filter), 0;
69         0,1/2*(1+filter)];
70 ss_filter=ss(matrix);
71 filter_u={'Vq_c','Vd_c'};
72 filter_y={'Uq_pos_c','Ud_pos_c'};
73 filter_uc_pos=ss(ss_filter.A,ss_filter.B,ss_filter.C,ss_filter.D,'
    inputname',filter_u,'outputname',filter_y);
74
75
76 %% u to uc rotating to qd values to converter reference
77
78 A_rot_uc=[0];
79 B_rot_uc=[0 0 0];
80 C_rot_uc=[0;0];
81 D_rot_uc=[cos(e_theta_1) -sin(e_theta_1) -sin(e_theta_1)*Vq_c_1-cos
    (e_theta_1)*Vd_c_1;
82           sin(e_theta_1) cos(e_theta_1) cos(e_theta_1)*Vq_c_1-sin(
    e_theta_1)*Vd_c_1];
83 rot_uc_x={' '};
84 rot_uc_u={'Uq_pll1','Ud_pll1','e_theta1'};
85 rot_uc_y={'Vq_c1','Vd_c1'};
86 rot_uc_1= ss(A_rot_uc,B_rot_uc,C_rot_uc,D_rot_uc,'StateName',
    rot_uc_x,'inputname',rot_uc_u,'outputname',rot_uc_y);
87
88 %% Filter
89 filter=tf([1,-4*100*pi,(2*100*pi)^2],[1,4*100*pi,(2*100*pi)^2]);
90 matrix=[1/2*(1+filter), 0;
91         0,1/2*(1+filter)];
92 ss_filter=ss(matrix);
93 filter_x={'state','state1'};
94 filter_u={'Vq_c1','Vd_c1'};
95 filter_y={'Uq_neg_c','Ud_neg_c'};
96 filter_uc_neg=ss(ss_filter.A,ss_filter.B,ss_filter.C,ss_filter.D,'
    inputname',filter_u,'outputname',filter_y);
97
98 %% i to ic rotating to qd values to converter reference
99
100 A_rot_ic=[0];
101 B_rot_ic=[0 0 0];
102 C_rot_ic=[0;0];
103 D_rot_ic=[cos(e_theta_0) -sin(e_theta_0) -sin(e_theta_0)*Iq_c_0-cos
    (e_theta_0)*Id_c_0;
104           sin(e_theta_0) cos(e_theta_0) cos(e_theta_0)*Iq_c_0-sin(
    e_theta_0)*Id_c_0];
105 rot_ic_x={' '};

```

```

106 rot_ic_u={'is_q' 'is_d','e_theta'};
107 rot_ic_y={'Iq_c','Id_c'};
108 rot_ic= ss(A_rot_ic,B_rot_ic,C_rot_ic,D_rot_ic,'StateName',rot_ic_x
    , 'inputname',rot_ic_u, 'outputname',rot_ic_y);
109
110
111 %% Filter
112 filter=tf([1,-4*100*pi,(2*100*pi)^2],[1,4*100*pi,(2*100*pi)^2]);
113 matrix=[1/2*(1+filter), 0;
114         0 ,1/2*(1+filter)];
115 ss_filter=ss(matrix);
116 filter_x={'state','state1'};
117 filter_u={'Iq_c','Id_c'};
118 filter_y={'Iq_pos_c','Id_pos_c'};
119 filter_ic_pos=ss(ss_filter.A,ss_filter.B,ss_filter.C,ss_filter.D,'
    inputname',filter_u, 'outputname',filter_y);
120
121
122 %% i to ic rotating to qd values to converter reference
123
124 A_rot_ic=[0];
125 B_rot_ic=[0 0 0];
126 C_rot_ic=[0;0];
127 D_rot_ic=[cos(e_theta_1) -sin(e_theta_1) -sin(e_theta_1)*Iq_c_1-cos
    (e_theta_1)*Id_c_1;
128           sin(e_theta_1) cos(e_theta_1) cos(e_theta_1)*Iq_c_1-sin(
    e_theta_1)*Id_c_1];
129 rot_ic_x={' '};
130 rot_ic_u={'is_q1' 'is_d1','e_theta1'};
131 rot_ic_y={'Iq_c1','Id_c1'};
132 rot_ic_1= ss(A_rot_ic,B_rot_ic,C_rot_ic,D_rot_ic,'StateName',
    rot_ic_x, 'inputname',rot_ic_u, 'outputname',rot_ic_y);
133
134 %% Filter
135 filter=tf([1,-4*100*pi,(2*100*pi)^2],[1,4*100*pi,(2*100*pi)^2]);
136 matrix=[1/2*(1+filter), 0;
137         0 ,1/2*(1+filter)];
138 ss_filter=ss(matrix);
139 filter_x={'state','state1'};
140 filter_u={'Iq_c1','Id_c1'};
141 filter_y={'Iq_neg_c','Id_neg_c'};
142 filter_ic_neg=ss(ss_filter.A,ss_filter.B,ss_filter.C,ss_filter.D,'
    inputname',filter_u, 'outputname',filter_y);
143
144 %% vcc to vc reserve transform
145
146 A_rot_vcc=[0];
147 B_rot_vcc=[0 0 0];
148 C_rot_vcc=[0;0];

```

```

149 D_rot_vcc=[cos(e_theta_0) sin(e_theta_0) -sin(e_theta_0)*Uq_c_0+cos
      (e_theta_0)*Ud_c_0;
150      -sin(e_theta_0) cos(e_theta_0) -cos(e_theta_0)*Uq_c_0-sin(
      e_theta_0)*Ud_c_0];
151 rot_vcc_x={' '};
152 rot_vcc_u={'Uq_c','Ud_c','e_theta'};
153 rot_vcc_y={'Vq_cc','Vd_cc'};
154 rot_vcc= ss(A_rot_vcc,B_rot_vcc,C_rot_vcc,D_rot_vcc,'StateName',
      rot_vcc_x,'inputname',rot_vcc_u,'outputname',rot_vcc_y);
155
156 %% vcc to vc reserve transform
157
158 A_rot_vcc=[0];
159 B_rot_vcc=[0 0 0];
160 C_rot_vcc=[0;0];
161 D_rot_vcc=[cos(e_theta_1) sin(e_theta_1) -sin(e_theta_1)*Uq_c_1+cos
      (e_theta_1)*Ud_c_1;
162      -sin(e_theta_1) cos(e_theta_1) -cos(e_theta_1)*Uq_c_1-sin(
      e_theta_1)*Ud_c_1];
163 rot_vcc_x={' '};
164 rot_vcc_u={'Uq_c1','Ud_c1','e_theta1'};
165 rot_vcc_y={'Vq_cc1','Vd_cc1'};
166 rot_vcc_1= ss(A_rot_vcc,B_rot_vcc,C_rot_vcc,D_rot_vcc,'StateName',
      rot_vcc_x,'inputname',rot_vcc_u,'outputname',rot_vcc_y);
167
168 %% P control
169
170 A_p_cont=[0];
171 B_p_cont=[0 0]; % I define Pref-Pmeas
172 C_p_cont=[0];
173 D_p_cont=[2/(3*Vq_c_0) 2/3*(-P_0/Vq_c_0^2)];
174 p_cont_x={' '};
175 p_cont_u={'Pref' 'Uq_pos_c'};
176 p_cont_y={'Iq_ref'};
177 p_cont = ss(A_p_cont,B_p_cont,C_p_cont,D_p_cont,'StateName',
      p_cont_x,'inputname',p_cont_u,'outputname',p_cont_y);
178
179 %% Q control
180
181 A_q_cont=[0];
182 B_q_cont=[0 0];
183 C_q_cont=[0];
184 D_q_cont=[2/(3*Vq_c_0) 2/3*(-Q_0/Vq_c_0^2)];
185 q_cont_x={' '};
186 q_cont_u={'Qref' 'Uq_pos_c'};
187 q_cont_y={'Id_ref'};
188 q_cont = ss(A_q_cont,B_q_cont,C_q_cont,D_q_cont,'StateName',
      q_cont_x,'inputname',q_cont_u,'outputname',q_cont_y);
189

```

```

190 %% Current control
191 w1=2*pi*50;
192 A_cc=[0 0;0 0];
193 B_cc=[1 0 -1 0 0 0;
194       0 1 0 -1 0 0];
195 C_cc=[-Ki_cl_1 0;
196       0 -Ki_cl_1];
197 D_cc=[-Kp_cl_1 0 Kp_cl_1 -w1*Ll_1 1 0;
198       0 -Kp_cl_1 w1*Ll_1 Kp_cl_1 0 1];
199 cc_x={'Ki_q_cc','Ki_d_cc'};
200 cc_u={'Iq_ref','Id_ref','Iq_pos_c','Id_pos_c','Uq_pos_c','Ud_pos_c'
      }; % 'Vq_VSC','Vd_VSC','Iq_VSC','Id_VSC' will come from the
      conversion matrixes
201 cc_y={'Uq_c_d','Ud_c_d'};
202 cc = ss(A_cc,B_cc,C_cc,D_cc,'StateName',cc_x,'inputname',cc_u,'
      outputname',cc_y);
203
204 %% Delay
205 [num,den]=pade(1e-4,20);
206 [A_d,B_d,C_d,D_d]=tf2ss(num,den);
207 d_x={'state_delay'};
208 d_u={'Uq_c_d'};
209 d_y={'Uq_c'};
210 d_1=ss(A_d,B_d,C_d,D_d,'inputname',d_u,'outputname',d_y);
211 d_x={'state_delay2'};
212 d_u={'Ud_c_d'};
213 d_y={'Ud_c'};
214 d_2=ss(A_d,B_d,C_d,D_d,'inputname',d_u,'outputname',d_y);
215
216 %% Current control
217 w2=-2*pi*50;
218 A_cc=[0 0;0 0];
219 B_cc=[-1 0 0 0;
220       0 -1 0 0];
221 C_cc=[-Ki_cl_1 0;
222       0 -Ki_cl_1];
223 D_cc=[Kp_cl_1 -w2*Ll_1 1 0;
224       w2*Ll_1 Kp_cl_1 0 1];
225 cc_x={'Ki_q_cc1','Ki_d_cc1'};
226 cc_u={'Iq_neg_c','Id_neg_c','Uq_neg_c','Ud_neg_c'}; % 'Vq_VSC','
      Vd_VSC','Iq_VSC','Id_VSC' will come from the conversion matrixes
227 cc_y={'Uq_c_d1','Ud_c_d1'};
228 cc_1 = ss(A_cc,B_cc,C_cc,D_cc,'StateName',cc_x,'inputname',cc_u,'
      outputname',cc_y);
229
230 %% Delay
231
232 [num,den]=pade(1e-4,20);
233 [A_d,B_d,C_d,D_d]=tf2ss(num,den);

```

```

234
235 d_x={'state_delay1'};
236 d_u={'Uq_c_d1'};
237 d_y={'Uq_c1'};
238 d_1_1=ss(A_d,B_d,C_d,D_d,'inputname',d_u,'outputname',d_y);
239 d_x={'state_delay21'};
240 d_u={'Ud_c_d1'};
241 d_y={'Ud_c1'};
242 d_2_1=ss(A_d,B_d,C_d,D_d,'inputname',d_u,'outputname',d_y);
243
244 %% PLL
245
246 A_pll=[0];
247 B_pll=[1];
248 C_pll=[-Ki_pll_1];
249 D_pll=[-Kp_pll_1];
250 pll_x={'Ki_PLL'};
251 pll_u={'Ud_pos_c'};
252 pll_y={'omega_PLL'};
253 pll = ss(A_pll,B_pll,C_pll,D_pll,'StateName',pll_x,'inputname',
          pll_u,'outputname',pll_y);
254
255
256
257 %% e theta (PLL-grid for rotating to converters reference)
258
259 A_theta=[0];
260 B_theta=[1 -1];
261 C_theta=[1];
262 D_theta=[0 0];
263 theta_x={'e_theta'};
264 theta_u={'omega_PLL','omega'};
265 theta_y={'e_theta'};
266 theta = ss(A_theta,B_theta,C_theta,D_theta,'StateName',theta_x,'
            inputname',theta_u,'outputname',theta_y);
267
268 %% e theta (PLL-grid for rotating to converters reference)
269
270 A_theta=[0];
271 B_theta=[-1 1];
272 C_theta=[1];
273 D_theta=[0 0];
274 theta_x={'e_theta1'};
275 theta_u={'omega_PLL','omega'};
276 theta_y={'e_theta1'};
277 theta1 = ss(A_theta,B_theta,C_theta,D_theta,'StateName',theta_x,'
              inputname',theta_u,'outputname',theta_y);
278
279 %% Converter

```

```

280
281 R_tr=Req_1;
282 L_tr=Leq_1;
283 A_vsc=[-(Req_1+Rl_1)/(Leq_1+Ll_1) -w1;
284         w1 -(Req_1+Rl_1)/(Leq_1+Ll_1)];
285 B_vsc=[-1/(Leq_1+Ll_1) 0 1/(Leq_1+Ll_1) 0; 0 -1/(Leq_1+Ll_1) 0 1/(
286         Leq_1+Ll_1)];
287 C_vsc=[1 0;
288         0 1;
289         (-R_tr+L_tr*(Rl_1+R_tr)/(Ll_1+L_tr)) 0;
290         0 (-R_tr+L_tr*(Rl_1+R_tr)/(Ll_1+L_tr))];
291 D_vsc=[0 0 0 0;
292         0 0 0 0;
293         L_tr/(Ll_1+L_tr) 0 (1-L_tr/(Ll_1+L_tr)) 0;
294         0 L_tr/(Ll_1+L_tr) 0 (1-L_tr/(Ll_1+L_tr))];
295 vsc_x={'is_q' 'is_d'};
296 vsc_u={'Vq_cc' 'Vd_cc' 'Uq_TH' 'Ud_TH' };
297 vsc_y={'is_q' 'is_d' 'Uq_pll' 'Ud_pll'};
298 vsc = ss(A_vsc,B_vsc,C_vsc,D_vsc,'StateName',vsc_x,'inputname',
299         vsc_u,'outputname',vsc_y);
300
301 %% Converter
302
303 R_tr=Req_1;
304 L_tr=Leq_1;
305 A_vsc=[-(Req_1+Rl_1)/(Leq_1+Ll_1) -w2;
306         w2 -(Req_1+Rl_1)/(Leq_1+Ll_1)];
307 B_vsc=[-1/(Leq_1+Ll_1) 0 1/(Leq_1+Ll_1) 0; 0 -1/(Leq_1+Ll_1) 0 1/(
308         Leq_1+Ll_1)];
309 C_vsc=[1 0;
310         0 1;
311         (-R_tr+L_tr*(Rl_1+R_tr)/(Ll_1+L_tr)) 0;
312         0 (-R_tr+L_tr*(Rl_1+R_tr)/(Ll_1+L_tr))];
313 D_vsc=[0 0 0 0;
314         0 0 0 0;
315         L_tr/(Ll_1+L_tr) 0 (1-L_tr/(Ll_1+L_tr)) 0;
316         0 L_tr/(Ll_1+L_tr) 0 (1-L_tr/(Ll_1+L_tr))];
317 vsc_x={'is_q1' 'is_d1'};
318 vsc_u={'Vq_cc1' 'Vd_cc1' 'Uq_TH1' 'Ud_TH1' };
319 vsc_y={'is_q1' 'is_d1' 'Uq_pll1' 'Ud_pll1'};
320 vsc_1 = ss(A_vsc,B_vsc,C_vsc,D_vsc,'StateName',vsc_x,'inputname',
321         vsc_u,'outputname',vsc_y);
322
323 %% Total model
324
325 VSC_total_pi_2 = connect(d_1,d_2,rot_vcc,rot_ic,rot_uc,p_cont,
326         q_cont,cc,pll,theta,vsc,d_1_1,d_2_1,rot_vcc_1,rot_ic_1,rot_uc_1,
327         cc_1,theta1,vsc_1,["Pref","Qref","Uq_TH", "Ud_TH", "omega", '

```

```
Uq_TH1 ', 'Ud_TH1 ', "omega"], {'Iq_pos_c ', 'Id_pos_c ', 'Uq_pos_c ', '
Ud_pos_c ', 'omega_PLL ', 'Iq_neg_c ', 'Id_neg_c ', 'Uq_neg_c ', 'Ud_neg_c
'});
```